

A Platform for Monitoring and Prediction of Social Impact and Acceptability of Modern Border Control Technology

Deliverable D4.1

User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis

Editor(s):	Andrei OGREZEANU, Radu GÂZĂ
Responsible Partner:	SIMAVI
Status-Version:	Final – v2.0
Date:	16/09/2021
Distribution level (CO, PU):	Public

Copyright message

© METICOS Consortium, 2021

This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both. Reproduction is authorised provided the source is acknowledged.

Project Number:	GA 883075
Project Title:	METICOS
Title of Deliverable:	User group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis
Due Date of Delivery to the EC:	28/02/2021
Workpackage responsible for the Deliverable:	WP4 - Domain Analysis, Requirements Engineering & Specifications Definition
Editor(s):	SIMAVI
Contributor(s):	All Partners
Reviewer(s):	AIT, EUC, ICCS
Approved by:	All Partners
Recommended/mandatory readers:	WP4 – WP9
Abstract:	First version of report on user group definitions, end-user needs and requirement analysis.
Keyword List:	End-user requirements
Disclaimer	This deliverable reflects only the author's views and views and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein

Document Description

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by
v0.0	16/12/2020	Table of contents	SIMAVI
v0.1	10/02/2021	First draft version	SIMAVI, with contributions from: ICCS, MAGG, AIT
v0.2	23/02/2021	Comments and suggestions received by consortium partners	ALL
v1.0	26/02/2021	Final version	SIMAVI
V2.0	16/09/2021	Final version updated in accordance with the comments received from review. Contributions from the NTNU and NET-U.	SIMAVI, NTNU, NET-U

Table of Contents

Table of Contents	4
List of Figures.....	6
List of Tables.....	7
Terms and abbreviations.....	8
Executive Summary	9
1 Introduction.....	10
1.1 Document objective and scope.....	10
1.2 Document structure	10
1.3 Relations to Other Work Packages, Tasks and Deliverables	10
1.4 Target audience.....	11
2 Methodological Approach.....	12
2.1 Methodological principles and approach.....	12
2.2 Activities and methods.....	14
2.2.1 DoA Analysis	15
2.2.2 Technologies and capabilities template	15
2.2.3 Preliminary Questionnaire for End User Partners.....	15
2.2.4 Preliminary meetings with end-users	16
2.2.5 End-users workshops.....	17
2.2.6 Post workshops questionnaire	17
3 Catalogue of Technologies and Capabilities.....	19
3.1 Overview of METICOS Technologies / Components	19
3.2 Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) Module – AIT.....	20
3.3 Socio-cultural Framework Module (FCSM) – NTNU	25
3.4 Automated Threshold Assessment Module (AThAM) – NTNU	28
3.5 Social Toolkit Module – NTNU.....	31
3.6 Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems Module / Interfaces with customs ID system – NET-U.....	36
3.7 Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data Module – ICCS	39
3.8 Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module – ICCS.....	44
3.9 Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis mechanisms Module – ICCS.....	48
3.10 Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module – ICCS	51
3.11 METICOS Middleware Module – MAGG.....	55
3.12 Smart Front-End Infrastructure Module – MAGG.....	59
3.13 Universal Connector with Modern BCP Risk Assessment Platform – SIMAVI.....	62
3.14 Data Integration Module – SIMAVI	64
3.15 Data Privacy Schemes – MAGG	66

4	User requirements	67
4.1	User role definitions	67
4.2	User requirements	69
4.2.1	Functional requirements	71
4.2.2	Non-Functional requirements	73
5	Conclusions.....	74
	References.....	75
	APPENDIX I: Replies to the questionnaire	76
	Cyprus police	76
	Hellenic Police	82
	Politsei- ja Piirivalveamet	85
	ITPF TIMISOARA	89
	APPENDIX II: Technologies and capabilities template	94
	General Introduction and Instructions.....	94
	Technology Description.....	94
	Capabilities	96

List of Figures

FIGURE 1 RELATIONS TO OTHER WORK PACKAGES	11
FIGURE 2: STAGES OF DEVELOPING DIFFERENT TYPES OF REQUIREMENTS AND SYSTEM DESIGN.	12
FIGURE 3: TASK 4.1; INPUTS, INSTRUMENTS, ACTIVITIES AND OUTPUTS	14
FIGURE 4 ETAP MODULE OVERVIEW	20
FIGURE 5: SOCIAL TOOLKIT MODULE	31
FIGURE 6 INTERACTIONS WITH NATIONAL, EU AND OTHER METICOS SERVICES	36
FIGURE 7 ADVANCED DATA MINING ENGINE (ADME) FOR STRUCTURED DATA MODULE.....	39
FIGURE 8 ADVANCED DATA MINING ENGINE (ADME) FOR UNSTRUCTURED DATA MODULE	44
FIGURE 9 CROSS-SECTORIAL (BIG) DATA ANALYSIS MECHANISMS MODULE.....	48
FIGURE 10 ARCHITECTURE OF THE DATA, TEXT AND VISUAL ANALYTICS COMPONENT	51
FIGURE 11 ARCHITECTURE OF THE METICOS MIDDLEWARE COMPONENT	56
FIGURE 12 SMART FRONT-END.....	59

List of Tables

TABLE 1: INTERNAL STAKEHOLDERS/CONSORTIUM MEMBERS' OVERVIEW.....	13
TABLE 2: METICOS TECHNOLOGIES / COMPONENTS	19
TABLE 3: EMBEDDED TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE PREDICTION (ETAP) MODULE DESCRIPTION.....	21
TABLE 4: EMBEDDED TECHNOLOGY ACCEPTANCE PREDICTION (ETAP) MODULE CAPABILITIES	23
TABLE 5: SOCIO-CULTURAL FRAMEWORK MODULE (SCFM) DESCRIPTION	25
TABLE 6: SOCIO-CULTURAL FRAMEWORK MODULE (SCFM) CAPABILITIES	27
TABLE 7: AUTOMATED THRESHOLD ASSESSMENT MODULE (ATHAM) DESCRIPTION	28
TABLE 8: AUTOMATED THRESHOLD ASSESSMENT MODULE (ATHAM) CAPABILITIES.....	30
TABLE 9: SOCIAL TOOLKIT MODULE DESCRIPTION	32
TABLE 10: SOCIAL TOOLKIT MODULE CAPABILITIES	35
TABLE 11: INTERFACES WITH BORDER MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS MODULE DESCRIPTION	37
TABLE 12: INTERFACES WITH BORDER MANAGEMENT INFORMATION SYSTEMS MODULE CAPABILITIES.....	38
TABLE 13: ADVANCED DATA MINING ENGINE (ADME) FOR STRUCTURED DATA MODULE DESCRIPTION	40
TABLE 14: ADVANCED DATA MINING ENGINE (ADME) FOR STRUCTURED DATA MODULE CAPABILITIES	43
TABLE 15: ADVANCED DATA MINING ENGINE (ADME) FOR UNSTRUCTURED DATA MODULE DESCRIPTION.....	44
TABLE 16: ADVANCED DATA MINING ENGINE (ADME) FOR UNSTRUCTURED DATA MODULE CAPABILITIES	47
TABLE 17: CROSS-SECTORIAL (BIG) DATA ANALYSIS MECHANISMS MODULE DESCRIPTION	48
TABLE 18: ADVANCED DATA MINING ENGINE (ADME) FOR UNSTRUCTURED DATA MODULE CAPABILITIES	50
TABLE 19: DATA, TEXT AND VISUAL ANALYTICS MODULE DESCRIPTION	51
TABLE 20: DATA, TEXT AND VISUAL ANALYTICS MODULE CAPABILITIES	54
TABLE 21: METICOS MIDDLEWARE MODULE DESCRIPTION	56
TABLE 22: METICOS MIDDLEWARE MODULE CAPABILITIES.....	58
TABLE 23: SMART FRONT-END INFRASTRUCTURE MODULE DESCRIPTION	60
TABLE 24: SMART FRONT-END INFRASTRUCTURE MODULE CAPABILITIES.....	61
TABLE 25: UNIVERSAL CONNECTOR WITH MODERN BCP RISK ASSESSMENT PLATFORM DESCRIPTION.....	62
TABLE 26: UNIVERSAL CONNECTOR WITH MODERN BCP RISK ASSESSMENT PLATFORM CAPABILITIES	63
TABLE 27: DATA INTEGRATION MODULE DESCRIPTION	64
TABLE 28: DATA INTEGRATION MODULE CAPABILITIES	65
TABLE 29: USER ROLE BY END-USER ORGANIZATION	68
TABLE 30: USER REQUIREMENTS	69

Terms and abbreviations

ADME	Advanced Data Mining Engine
AIT	AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH
API	Application Programming Interface
AThAM	Automated Threshold Assessment Module
BCP	Border Control Point
CYPOL	Cyprul Police
DoA	Description of Action
DTVA	Data, Text and Visual Analytics (module)
EC	European Commission
ETAP	Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (Module)
EU	The European Union
EUC	EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY CYPRUS
HDF	Hierarchical Data Format
ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS
JOAFG	JOHANNITER OSTERREICH AUSBILDUNG UND FORSCHUNG GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH
MAGG	MAGGIOLI SPA
N/A	Not Avalailable
NET-U	NET-U CONSULTANTS LTD
NTNU	NORGES TEKNISKNATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET
R&D	Research and Development
REST	Representational state transfer
SCFM	socio-cultural framework module
SIMAVI	SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL
SQL	Structured Query Language
TAM	Technology Acceptance Model
TRL	Technology Readiness Level
UTAUT	Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology
VUB	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL
WCAG 2.0	Web Content Accessibility Guidelines
Wi-Fi	wireless network protocols
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The current document aims to present the end-user requirements for the resulting METICOS system.

In order to define the most appropriate end-user requirements, this document focuses on the main objectives of the WP4 package, namely to improve the extraction, integration and sharing of cross-sectoral data, taking into account the operating environments of the consortium's border authorities.

In this context, this deliverable:

- describes methodological principles and approach to define user requirements;
- describes the activities carried out to identify user requirements:
 - ✓ analysis of the Description of Action (DoA) document (Parts A and B) to define the scope and objectives of T4.1 and D4.1 and to identify user requirements, roles, and technologies and capabilities.
 - ✓ use of the Technologies and Capabilities template to collect high and medium level descriptions of technologies (and their capabilities) available on the METICOS Project. This information was used to inform the user requirements but was also collected with a view to later definition of system specifications, use cases and architectural design of the METICOS Platform.
 - ✓ use of a preliminary questionnaire in order to collect the necessary information and requirements regarding the METICOS solution envisaged for measuring the social acceptance of Smart Border Control technologies, as well as for identifying user groups, end users and their needs.
 - ✓ organization of workshops for end users through which user requirements were opened for discussions, additions, changes.
- presents the functionalities and capabilities of the METICOS system components;
 - ✓ the Technologies and Capabilities template has been completed by each technology partner once for each technology for which they are responsible. Based on these responses, high and medium level descriptions of the technologies (and their capabilities) available in the METICOS project were identified.
 - ✓ In addition, each technology partner provided an introductory description consisting of text and schematics for each of their components / technologies.
- presents the identified potential roles;
 - ✓ based on questions 6 and 7 of the preliminary questionnaire used in the analysis activity, a number of potential user roles were identified.
 - ✓ The result of this analysis can be found in the chapter [4.1 User role definitions](#)
- presents the first identified requirements of the end users.
 - ✓ following the activities carried out to identify user requirements, a number of 9 functional requirements and 4 non-functional requirements were identified
 - ✓ the first results of our user requirements elicitation and analysis can be found in the chapter [4.2 User requirements](#)

This deliverable is intended to be a regularly updated document based on information about available end-user data and other functionalities to cover end-user requirements.

1 Introduction

1.1 Document objective and scope

This task and deliverable conduct and present the end-user requirements analysis for the entire METICOS Project and the resulting METICOS System. As such the general objective of the project defines also the purpose and scope of the analysis carried out under T4.1. The overall objective of the project is to develop a platform that correlates the data collected from different data sources to identify the social acceptance of Smart Border Control technologies, including aspects of more efficient border management, quality of service, etc.

In order to meet the objective of the project, the needs of end-users will be identified and the requirements for improving the extraction, integration and sharing of data will be identified, taking into account the operating environments of the border authorities within the consortium.

This Task and Deliverable directly answers WP4 first objective to “Define the requirements for enhanced cross-sectorial data mining, integration and sharing taking into account the operation environments of the border authorities within the consortium.” (DoA, Part A, p.23).

1.2 Document structure

The document is structured into the following 6 sections:

- Chapter 1 “Introduction” introduces the intended audience of the document and its structure.
- Chapter 2 “Methodological Approach” explains to the intended audience the methodological approach in achieving the deliverable
- Chapter 3 “Stakeholders overview”
- Chapter 4 “Catalogue of Technologies and Capabilities” contains the answers received to the Technology and Capabilities template
- Chapter 5 “User requirements” contains the list of end user requirements as well as the end user interest level for each requirement.
- Chapter 6 “Conclusions” consists of the conclusions of this deliverable report

1.3 Relations to Other Work Packages, Tasks and Deliverables

Task 4.1 produces outputs that represent inputs for the other tasks in different packages. This task / deliverable are closely related to the other tasks / deliverables as follows:

- In Task 4.1 stakeholder are identified for quantification of social acceptance of a specific border control technology solution (WP5)
- Task 4.1 provides a preliminary identification of users' requirements for continuous monitoring of acceptance and simulation technology, which will be detailed in WP6
- The task 7.1 (WP7) will deal with the definition and collection of all datasets, information that is initially based on the user requirements identified in task 4.1
- In task T8.1 (WP8) it will be necessary to analyse and describe the data to be collected in order to design its relational structure and its logical database representation to be designed. This analyse is initially based on the user requirements identified in task 4.1.

- The goal of task T9.3 (WP9) is to provide an Interactive Visual Analytics module in order to visualize, analyse and explore the data obtained from WP3, WP4 and WP5.

Figure 1 Relations to Other Work Packages

1.4 Target audience

This document is addressed to both members of the consortium and the general public.

2 Methodological Approach

2.1 Methodological principles and approach

This project follows a state-of-the-art succession to designing the METICOS System as illustrated in Figure 2 below.

Figure 2: Stages of developing different types of requirements and system design.

This document is primarily focused on *User requirements* for the METICOS System. User requirements are understood as “tasks or goals the users must be able to perform with the product that will provide value to someone. (...) User requirements describe what the user will be able to do with the system.” (Wieggers and Beatty, 2013, p. 9). It should be noted that other types of requirements, i.e. technical and architectural are left for later deliverables (i.e. further iterations of T4.1/D4.1 and, T4.3, D4.3).

To define user requirements, we follow an approach inspired by *cooperative design* (or in short *co-design*), which we think is appropriate for a project implemented in a wide consortium of 15 partners. *Co-design* (also termed in different contexts *participatory design*, *cooperative design*, or *co-creation*) refers to designing products, technological systems, etc. with an active participation and collaboration of various types of relevant actors (or stakeholders) such as designers, developers, customers, users, etc (Steen et al., 2011). A particular stakeholder group emphasized in *co-design* is the involvement of users, not just in passive capacity of rubberstamping system specifications, but as active actors and “competent practitioners” who have important knowledge to share in the design process (Carroll, 2004; Greenbaum and Kyng, 1991).

Applied to the METICOS Project, and Task 4.1, *co-design* means a concern for the active involvement of the various stakeholders (primarily, to begin with, internal stakeholders, i.e. Consortium Members and their personnel, but possibly expanding on this circle as the project progresses) in their various capacities and roles. The major classification of internal stakeholders by their role and type of implication in relation to the METICOS System (Note: this is different from the “project role” in terms of partner’s leadership or contributor position as related to Tasks, Work Packages or the entire Project):

- **End User/Pilot Organizations:** the partners/member of consortium who will be involved in using/piloting the METICOS System as end users/practitioners in the area of border control. They contribute to the project with their business expertise in the area of border control; they are a main actor in defining and validating user requirements as well as in piloting the System. Five (5) such organizations are present in the Project, to see specifically who they are see Table 1 below, last column.¹
- **Technology Provider Partners:** are members of the consortium who are in charge of providing technological solutions (either as responsible for components development or as integrators). Seven (7) such organizations are present in the Project, to see specifically who they are see Table 1 below, last column.
- **Other Expertise/Service Provider Partners** – partners who are in neither category above, but have distinct role providing other expertise and/or services within the Project. Three (3) such organizations are present in the Project, to see specifically who they are see Table 1 below, last column.

Table 1: Internal stakeholders/consortium members' overview

Partner #	Short name	Partner Name	Country	Organization type	Role as related to METICOS System
1	EUC	EUROPEAN UNIVERSITY CYPRUS	CYPRUS	UNI	The coordinator
2	ICCS	INSTITUTE OF COMMUNICATION AND COMPUTER SYSTEMS	Greece	RI	Technology Provider
3	NetU	NET-U CONSULTANTS LTD	Cyprus	SME	Technology Provider
4	NTNU	NORGES TEKNISKNATURVITENSKAPELIGE UNIVERSITET NTNU	Norway	UNI	Technology Provider
5	VUB	VRIJE UNIVERSITEIT BRUSSEL	Belgium	UNI	Other
6	SIMAVI	SOFTWARE IMAGINATION & VISION SRL	Romania	LE	Technology Provider
7	AIT	AIT AUSTRIAN INSTITUTE OF TECHNOLOGY GMBH	Austria	UNI	Technology Provider
8	JOAFG	JOHANNITER OSTERREICH AUSBILDUNG UND FORSCHUNG GEMEINNUTZIGE GMBH	Austria	NGO	Other
9	MAGG	MAGGIOLI SPA	Italy	LE	Technology Provider
10	VILABS	VILABS OE	Greece	SME	Other
11	MoCP/ED PD	YPIRESIA DIACHEIRISIS EUROPAIKON KAI ANAPTYXIAKON PROGRAMMATON (Y.D.E.A.P.)	Greece	NGO	End User
12	PPA	Politsei- ja Piirivalveamet	Estonia	NGO	End User
13	ITPFT	INSPECTORATUL TERITORIAL AL POLITIEI DE FRONTIERA TIMISOARA	Romania	NGO	End User
14	ASBGS	ADMINISTRATION OF THE STATE BORDER GUARD SERVICE OF UKRAINE	Ukraine	NGO	End User
15	CYPOL	Cyprus police	Cyprus	NGO	End User

¹ End User Organizations are not to be confused with end users at the individual level. At individual level end user roles are defined and identified in Section 4.1.

2.2 Activities and methods

To arrive at a first formalization of user requirements for the METICOS System, a variety of information sources, instruments and activities were used. Figure 3 below provides an overview of such information sources (inputs and instruments), activities and outputs.

Figure 3: Task 4.1; Inputs, Instruments, Activities and Outputs

We describe below each of the instruments used and activities carried out.

2.2.1 DoA Analysis

A careful analysis of the Description of Action (DoA) document (parts A and B) was carried out to define the scope and objectives of T4.1 and D4.1 and to make use of work that had been carried out during Project definition. The DoA was thus one of the sources in identifying user requirements but also in identifying and defining the role of Technologies and Capabilities (for the later see Section 2.2.2)

2.2.2 Technologies and capabilities template

Many of the activities described below were focused on end users' organizations. However, to make use of information about Technologies/Components of the METICOS System and their capabilities we created a template to request this information from Technology Provider Partners.

The objective of the Technologies and Capabilities template is to provide high and medium level descriptions of technologies (and their capabilities) available on the METICOS Project. This information was used to inform the user requirements but was also collected with a view to later definition of system specifications, use cases and architectural design of the METICOS Platform.

The template contains two tables. The first provides a high-level description of METICOS technologies / components, and the second table describes the functionalities/capabilities of the technology (existing or proposed to be developed in this project).

The template was developed by SIMAVI and proposed for discussion to the technical partners in the meetings held on the WP4 package. It was then sent for consultation to the technical partners, and the final form of the template was sent to the technical partners to complete for each technology.

The template can be found in APPENDIX II: Technologies and capabilities template.

The answers to the templates can be found in Chapter 3 Catalogue of Technologies and Capabilities.

2.2.3 Preliminary Questionnaire for End User Partners

The objectives of the preliminary questionnaire are:

- ✓ to gather by necessary information and requirements regarding the envisaged METICOS solution for measuring the social acceptance of Smart Border Control technologies.
- ✓ to identify user groups, end users and their needs.

The answers to the questions contained in the questionnaire helped us to better model the METICOS solution, so as to cover the needs of stakeholders.

The questionnaire was created together by SIMAVI and ICCS and covered the following issues:

- ✓ the Border Control Point(s) (BCP) that the pilot will take place (the exact location, the type of border, traffic)
- ✓ description of the process(es) that are being used at the Border Control Point
- ✓ existing KPIs to measure the efficiency of the processes and the social acceptance of the Smart Border Control technologies

- ✓ the categories of people that that the beneficiary envisage the METICOS project to measure their acceptance of the Smart Border technologies
- ✓ other stakeholders, apart from beneficiary authority/organization, which would need access to the social acceptance and impact that we will measure and are potential future users of the METICOS solution
- ✓ user groups and end users who will access the offered METICOS platform
- ✓ description of their activity and the procedures used in their activity
- ✓ currently used applications and data that the end users use in their work

The questionnaires were sent to all end-user partners and we did not receive a response from the Administration of the State Border Guard Service of Ukraine.

At the time of delivery the discussions were on going and therefore could not involve the Ukrainian partners and at this time we are on standby to involve the Ukrainian partners for requirements elicitation.

The definition of a use case in Ukraine was a challenge from the beginning of METICOS, as according to the EU – Ukraine Association Agreement, **Ukraine agreed** to implement European personal data protection regulation (including the GDPR) into national legislation. Considering that we need to include additional agreements with Ukrainian border authorities on the use and protection of the data we will collect in their pilot activities. In the GA pp 171 (part-B, section 1.3.2) we are mentioning that ***'the trials and data collection will be done in European region, in order to be aligned with GDPR rules.'*** Currently we discussing with Ukraine the possibility to organise a use case on the EU part of their borders, but this needs time as we need to have also the agreement of the EU part.

The answers to the questionnaires can be found in APPENDIX I: Replies to the questionnaire.

2.2.4 Preliminary meetings with end-users

MAGG and ICCS had preliminary meetings with Cyprus Police and Hellenic Police on the 22nd and 23rd December 2020 respectively. In these meetings:

- the scope and target of METICOS was presented
- It was clearly specified that the objective of METICOS is not to create a new SBC solution, but to measure the acceptance of current and new SBC technologies.
- CYPOL mentioned that data processed by the kiosks installed in Larnaka airport (BORDERXPRESS solution) are interlinked with all the EU relevant systems (VIS, ETIAS,...)
- CYPOL specified that currently there is no data to measure the time required to cross border control and this type of data is not stored
- End-users expects from us a template with the data we need in order to get the necessary input and fill it in – to be sent to all the end-user pilot partners

For this meetings meeting minutes and PowerPoint presentations were prepared and they are available online in the project work file and are available to reviewers upon request.

2.2.5 End-users workshops

The End-users workshops represented one of the main means by which the user requirements were opened for discussion, additions, modifications. 2 workshops were organized with the participation of end-users and all technical partners, as follows:

- On 26th January with:
 - o Cyprus Police (3 persons)
 - o Hellenic Police (9 persons)
 - o Institute Of Communication And Computer Systems (3 persons)
 - o Johanniter Österreich Ausbildung und Forschung Gemeinnützige GmbH (1 person)
 - o Maggioli SPA (1 person)
 - o Software Imagination & Vision SRL (3 persons)
- On 27th January with:
 - o Politsei- ja Piirivalveamet (5 persons)
 - o Inspectoratul Teritorial al Politiei de Frontiera Timisoara (1 person)
 - o Institute Of Communication And Computer Systems (1 person)
 - o Johanniter Österreich Ausbildung und Forschung Gemeinnützige GmbH (2 persons)
 - o Maggioli SPA (1 person)
 - o Software Imagination & Vision SRL (3 persons)

We also invited people from the Administration of the State Border Service of Ukraine to the workshop, but they did not respond to our invitation. We will involve them in the next iteration, when we will include the impact to non EU citizens.

In these meetings:

- A short presentation was made by ICCS about the objectives and purpose of METICOS and the types of data we will need to collect.
- A short presentation was made by SIMAVI about the objectives and purpose of task 4.1 and of deliverable D4.1.
- A short presentation was made by ICCS about the template for identifying available data, which are grouped into: historical data and real-time data. This template will be sent to end-users who may propose the collection of other data sets.
- A list of proposed requirements to which end-users need to provide feedback will be sent to end-users, as well as a template for existing datasets to be submitted and completed by all pilot partners

The workshops were recorded and meeting minutes were prepared and they are available online in the project work file and can be sent to reviewers upon request.

2.2.6 Post workshops questionnaire

After the workshops, the list of end-user requirements was closer to being final. One of the conclusions of the Workshops was that some of the participants felt better to have additional time to consider the requirements discussed and provide some inputs in writing. In addition, we wanted to have a more systematic way to gauge the level of interest of End User Organizations in the various

requirements. To these ends a Post-workshop questionnaire was created asking three questions about each identified requirement:

1. Are there any comments or specifics of this requirement you would like to highlight? (i.e. you can insist on some details, or phrase more concretely what you would need) (please answer separately for each requirement below) Do you think the text of the requirement description needs to be changed (made more specific in some way)? Do you have suggestions in this regard? If so, please propose here the changed text.
2. To what extent do you think there would be problems (technical, legal, etc.) for your institution to provide data necessary for this kind of requirement/future functionalities?
3. Aside from any feasibility concerns (ignoring for the moment any possible legal, technical issues that we will have to deal with later), to what extent your institution finds this requirement important (i.e. it is of interest for your institution within the METICOS Project)? (use the scale provided: 0 - Not at all important; 1 - Somewhat important; 2 - Important; 3 - Very Important)

This questionnaire was first discussed in WP4 meetings with technological partners .

End-user requirements as well as the level of end-user interest for each requirement can be viewed in Section 4.2 User requirements.

3 Catalogue of Technologies and Capabilities

This chapter presents the Technologies/Components of the METICOS System and their expected functionalities/capabilities. This chapter represents still an early view of the components, but a further iteration from the understanding at the DoA writing stage. Nevertheless, the understanding of the components and their capabilities is expected to be further refined as we progress toward further user requirements analysis, technical/system requirements and specifications and architectural specifications. The purpose of this chapter and the analysis that accompanied it is to support [Chapter 4 User requirements](#) and further analysis on technical requirements and specifications (under T4.1) as well as work toward defining the System Architecture (under T4.3).

This chapter, and its following subsections (except the very next) are mainly based on the Technologies and Capabilities Template described in Section 2.2.2, which was filled in by each Technology Provider Partner once per each technology they are responsible for. In addition, each Technology Provider Partner has provided an introductory description consisting of text and schematics for each of their components/technologies.

3.1 Overview of METICOS Technologies / Components

This Section provides an overview of the METICOS Technologies/Components and the Technology Provider Partners in charge of developing them.

Table 2: METICOS Technologies / Components

Relevant Products/ Technology	TRL Current	TRL Target	Task	Responsible (cf. Part A)
Data Integration Module	3	8	T9.2	SIMAVI
Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) - Unstructured Data	3	6	T7.3	ICCS
Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) - Structured Data	3	6	T7.4	ICCS
Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) module.	2	5	T5.4	AIT
Cross-sectorial (big) data analysis mechanisms	2	6	T7.5	ICCS
Data, Text & Visual Analytics Toolkit	4	5	T9.3	SIMAVI
METICOS Data Privacy Schemes ²	2	5	T8.2	MAGG
METICOS Middleware	3	5	T8.2	MAGG
Smart Front-End Infrastructure	4	5	T8.5	MAGG
Universal Connector with Modern BCP Risk Assessment Platform	3	5	T9.2	SIMAVI

² It is no longer considered a component. See section 3.15

Interfaces with customs identification systems	2	5	T8.3	NetU
Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems	2	5	T8.3	NetU
Socio-cultural framework Module	2	5	T6.3	NTNU
Automated Threshold Assessment Module	3	5	T6.3	NTNU
Social Toolkit	1	5	T6.3	NTNU

3.2 Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) Module – AIT

The Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) module quantifies social acceptance of a specific border control technology solution by predicting the likelihood of acceptance/non-acceptance by a person belonging to one of the two targeted groups (travelers, border authorities). The ETAP module is based on one or more probabilistic technology acceptance models (TAMs) which are developed during the project. Each TAM consists of several components that reflect the most relevant key aspects (perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, etc.) of acceptance of smart border control technologies.

The ETAP module takes the relevant features describing the different groups of influence factors (border control technology used, user characteristics, selected contextual variable) as input. These input features are provided by the (Border) Signal Processing, the Cross-sectorial (big) data analysis mechanisms and the Advanced Data Mining Engine. The output of the module is a score vector describing the likelihood of acceptance as well as related metrics like ‘intention to use’. This output is used by the DTVA and Big Data engines, depending on the actual use case at hand.

Figure 4 ETAP Module Overview

Table 3: Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) Module Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	AIT
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) Module
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	ETAP
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T5.4 (Model Development), T5.5 (Algorithm Development)
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	developed and owned by AIT
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 2 – technology concept formulated
Technology/Component History	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	<p>The ETAP Module is based on TAM (Technology Acceptance Model, Davis et al. 1989). The concept has been adapted and extended during the last decades (TAM2, TAM3, UTAUT,...) and has been applied in various application concepts. At AIT, we use acceptance modelling to accompany product and service development processes to guarantee user friendly outputs.</p> <p>Every acceptance model need to be designed for a specific use case. Thus, at the beginning of the project requirements and scenario-specific information is collected to develop an acceptance model. During the execution of the related tasks, empirical data based on surveys is added to the model to quantify acceptance.</p>
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	<p>The ETAP module receives a tuple of input information (border control technology in focus, user description) describing a single case (user-technology interaction). The ETAP module will then predict likely acceptance/non-acceptance of given border control technology solution by defined target users or user groups, grounded on probabilistic technology acceptance models (TAMs). To this end, it will process feature data describing relevant influence factors and generate a score vector describing likelihood of acceptance as well as other related metrics required by the Data Integration Module and Big Data engine.</p> <p>Configuration is foreseen on for Admin users: - model import/export</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - manual model update - evt. activate/deactivate certain parts of the model (TBD) - activate/deactivate online model retraining - monitor/roll back online mode retraining
<p>Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits</p>	<p>With the ETAP module, the likeliness of acceptance of certain border crossing technologies can be estimated in advance.</p> <p>Presentation/Reporting depends on the actual use case and will most likely be in the form of dashboards/widgets or reports. However, there is not dedicated "ETAP Report" foreseen, because technically, the module is is just a stream processor that processes single cases (see above).</p> <p>Potential use cases (non-exhaustive list):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> •Assessing acceptability of installations at BCP •Supporting prediction of stakeholder decision-making and behavior in real-time •Understanding driving factors behind acceptance •Assessing impact of BC technology change
<p>Data Input Requirements</p>	<p>Each input tuple (consisting of a number of key/value pairs) represents one case/observation (technology, user).</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Technology types & descriptions - User-related data (background, demographics, travel-related parameters) - Model-retraining data: in this case, the above data is extended with hints regarding likely acceptance (e.g. answers of a traveler who filled out a questionnaire in the field)
<p>Expected Data Output</p>	<p>Depends on the use case:</p> <p>Level 1 (basic): acceptance/intention to use</p> <p>Level 2: key factor levels (ease of use, etc.)</p> <p>Level 3: detailed factor levels & influence weights</p> <p>Technically, this data will be provided in the form of a set of key-value pairs on a per case/estimation basis.</p>
<p>Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces</p>	<p>Nothing special hardware, since only communication via IP networking protocols within the METICOS platform.</p>
<p>Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)</p>	<p>Docker, nginx, python, REST - Interface (if needed with swagger UI), nodeJS</p>
<p>Other Information, Observations, etc.</p>	<p>The validated TAM prototype algorithm will be implemented as a Python/R module for the METICOS platform. We expect communication via a RESTful interface.</p>

Table 4: Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction (ETAP) Module Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Quantification of social acceptance of a specific border control technology solution	The ETAP module is grounded on one or more probabilistic technology acceptance models (TAMs) which are developed during the project. The probabilistic modelling will be based on existing literature (technology acceptance, expectancy and quality of experience research, existing acceptance models) as well as datasets generated during the project by means of user studies and surveys. The model itself consists of several components that reflect the most relevant key aspects (perceived usefulness, perceived ease of use, trust, etc.) of acceptance of smart border control technologies.	Border control authorities, Border control technology providers, Policy makers	TRL 2 – technology concept formulated	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	<p>Input: The ETAP module takes the relevant features describing the different groups of influence factors (border control technology used, user characteristics, usage context) as input. These input features are provided by the (Border) Signal Processing, the Cross-sectorial (big) data analysis mechanisms and the Advanced Data Mining Engine</p> <p>Output: The output of the module is a score vector describing the likelihood of acceptance as well as related metrics like ‘intention to use’. This output is used by the DSS and Big Data engines</p>

<p>User Interface (End User)</p>	<p>End user -> Dashboard widgets -> Beispiele The interface displays numerical values (e.g. percent) representing acceptance related factors (e.g., intention to use, easiness of usages, trust, etc)based on the calculations of the ETAP module. Dashboard widgets are used to display these values, e.g., gauge, bullet graphs, bar chars, etc.)</p>	<p>Border control authorities, Border control technology providers, Policy makers</p>	<p>TRL 2 – technology concept formulated</p>	<p>TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment</p>	<p>Input: score vector describing the likelihood of acceptance as well as related metrics like ‘intention to use’. Output: metrics are displayed via widgets (e.g. gauge ranging from 0% to 100% regarding intention to use). Evt. also a simple presentation of the status of the online model retraining. widgets are integrated in the METICOS GUI</p>
<p>User Interface (Admin User)</p>	<p>This is an extension to the interface for end users (see line above). An admin user is able to change several parameters of the underlying ETAP module to evaluate how acceptance is affected if e.g. demographic aspects of travelers are changed.</p>	<p>Administrators</p>	<p>TRL 2 – technology concept formulated</p>	<p>TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment</p>	<p>Input: score vector describing the likelihood of acceptance as well as related metrics like ‘intention to use’. + Configuration interface to change model parameters (e.g. range sliders or drop down list for all relevant parameters) Output: metrics are displayed via widgets (e.g. gauge ranging from 0% to 100% regarding intention to use). Status of the model retraining. widgets are integrated in the METICOS GUI. Eventually, the module provides some logging accessible for admin/dev users,</p>

3.3 Socio-cultural Framework Module (FCSM) – NTNU

The socio-cultural framework module (SCFM) will allow the METICOS platform to assess the main reasons behind possible misunderstandings that may occur when individuals with different sociocultural backgrounds will try to pass through new BCP technologies. This module will provide inputs to the METICOS Social Toolkit. The module will use multiple parameters related to the sociocultural background and beyond, such as age, gender, social status, education, professional status, religion, lifestyle, native language, gestures etc., while other relevant external parameters might be related to context-based data, such as location, time etc.

Also, a certain culture is made up of specific norms and values, and different cultures can often be related to different norms and underlying values, which should be strictly taken into account when applying new BCP technologies that affect most people moving on a daily basis or even those moving for the first time abroad. Besides these parameters, another possible direction would be to understand the motivation of the people moving through BCPs and how is that relates to their socio-cultural background and to the values and norms or even lifestyle they are willing to adhere to, so as to assess whether this could reflect possible situations of misunderstanding.

Table 5: Socio-cultural framework Module (SCFM) Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	NTNU
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	Socio-cultural Framework
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	SCFM
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T6.3 - METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	The tool will be developed by NTNU.
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 2 – technology concept formulated
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	The component has been proposed during the writing of the proposal. There were different research papers consulted before the idea was placed.
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	The technology is not available yet, while the main technology concepts have been formulated. We are already aware of the main parameters needed to accomplish the tasks related with this component and we are working towards reaching the upcoming stages, in collaboration with the other partners involved.

Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	<p>The socio-cultural framework module (SCFM) will allow the METICOS platform to assess the main reasons behind possible misunderstandings that may occur when individuals with different sociocultural backgrounds will try to pass through new BCP technologies. This module will provide inputs to the METICOS Social Toolkit. The module will use multiple parameters, based on primarily synthetic data, related to the sociocultural background and beyond, such as age, gender, social status, education, professional status, religion, lifestyle, native language, gestures etc., while other relevant external parameters might be related to context-based data, such as location, time etc. The main inputs from this module should be able to provide a set of relevant parameters for addressing the socio-cultural parameters that affect the final acceptance rate for a given BCP technology.</p>
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	<p>The main benefit deriving from SCFM will be related to understanding the main parameters that affect the acceptance rate of no-gate solutions for the average traveller, as related to their socio-cultural background. The end users will be able to see the main parameters from the module and compare it with given cases to understand more about the context. The module will also share inputs and feedback with the Social sensing toolkit, in an attempt to continuously improve the outcomes for a better decision making process</p>
Data Input Requirements	<p>We do not expect the necessity of specific hardware interfaces for this module</p>
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	<p>We do not expect the necessity of specific hardware interfaces for this module</p>
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	<p>This part is still under investigation</p>
Other Information, Observations, etc.	

Table 6: Socio-cultural Framework Module (SCFM) Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Define input parameters:	After collecting relevant information about state-of-the-art for the relevant work in the previous tasks, we will be able to define the final list of parameters as appropriate inputs to the SCFM, such as age, gender, social status, education, lifestyle etc. along with appropriate values as related to the objectives set for this task	NTNU	TRL 2 – technology concept formulated	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	This part is still under investigation
Define output parameters:	Here we will also make use of completed work/deliverables to be able to define a final list of parameters as appropriate outputs to the module, that will be continuously revised in terms of their impact on the final decision making process	NTNU	TRL 2 - technology concept	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	This is still being under investigation, main part of the current research plan. Might be same interface with the input level above
Map input and output parameters	The ongoing tasks will help us define the appropriate model explaining the relationship between the input and output parameters - the main equation - that should provide optimal solution to the task given. This will also be part of a continuous process aiming for the best solutions	NTNU	TRL 2 – technology concept formulated	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	This part is still under investigation

3.4 Automated Threshold Assessment Module (AThAM) – NTNU

The Automated Threshold Assessment Module (AThAM) will define a specific threshold for each BCP technology when dealing with non-EU travellers. It will be an external component supporting the METICOS Social Toolkit with continuous feeds from real-time data. The module will use information collected from different sources, mostly related to the different technologies and devices in use, such as the overall complexity of the device/technology used, the level of interaction with different users, response time, the level of flexibility, level of necessary support from border authorities etc. Similar with the SCFM, AThAM will aim to use context-based data to adjust the threshold accordingly. Initial values of thresholds will be obtained from local authorities, based on their experience and knowledge from existing BCP technologies used, along with national and EU legislation norms related to this problem. These values will be matched with the existing BCP technologies to define a model that will explain the threshold level based on the parameters above and others introduced further.

The module will incorporate several tools, ranging from simple regression tools to more advanced machine learning models, in order to define the best model predicting the level of threshold for each BCP technology, while trying to make the travellers feel satisfied with the entire process. Then, since the problem is highly sensitive and difficult to address in its whole diversity on an individual basis, simulation tools could be a good and efficient way to show results that can be further mapped to real cases of individuals passing through border control.

Table 7: Automated Threshold Assessment Module (AThAM) Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	NTNU
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	Automated Threshold Assessment Module
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	AThAM
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T6.3 - METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	The tool will be developed by NTNU.
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	The component was proposed as an important module related to the Social sensing toolkit. It was initially proposed for this project, while considering relevant development of similar components in the related disciplines of study.

Technology/Component in the Present: Description	The component is not available yet, while it is in a proof of concept stage. We are in the final stages of defining the main parameters needed for the component to accomplish the objectives given, as part of T6.3. Most of initial data sources are related to existing hardware and software specifications, as well as existing regulations and legal practices in place in the relevant BCPs.
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	This module will be able to define a specific threshold for each BCP technology when dealing with non-EU travellers, supporting the Social sensing toolkit with continuous feeds of data. There will be several tools incorporated in order to define the best model predicting the level of threshold for each BCP technology, while trying to make the travellers feel satisfied with the entire process.
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	The module will use information collected from different sources, mostly related to the different technologies and devices in use, i.e. the overall complexity of the device/technology used, the level of interaction with different users, response time, the level of flexibility, level of necessary support from border authorities etc., along with context-based data to adjust the threshold accordingly. We aim to use a range of different methods and associated advanced tools in order to support an entirely new simulation platform, that would be linked to the other tools and engines within the same environment, in order to help achieve the final objectives of monitoring parameters values from time to time and support decision making process for the end users.
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	We do not expect the need for specific hardware interfaces on this module
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	This part is still under investigation
Other Information, Observations, etc.	

Table 8: Automated Threshold Assessment Module (ATHAM) Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Define main input parameters	As related to the acceptance rate for diverse BCP technologies, this module should help us define the main parameters needed in the process. We will consider different sources of information when it comes to the given technology and other context-related data	NTNU, Border authorities	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	This part is in the final stages of investigation
Define the input-output relation	The module should be able to make use of the advanced tools and methods incorporated to decide properly the best-fit model for providing outcomes of high relevance to the Social sensing toolkit, in terms of the BCP technologies involved	NTNU, Border authorities	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	This part is under investigation
Define the specific threshold for each BCP technology	Once the main input parameters and the model is properly defined, the module should be able to correctly tune the threshold level for a given BCP technology, based also on local context. The whole process will be affected from continuous updates based on feedback from existing modules within the Social sensing toolkit and others.	NTNU, Border authorities	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	This part is under investigation

3.5 Social Toolkit Module – NTNU

In METICOS project, the Social Toolkit Module will contribute into achieving the objective of continuously **monitoring the social acceptance considering the different behavioural patterns of the people and the interactions between them** trying to pass the EU border control systems. Since the final objective would be to evolve towards *a safe and effective no gate solution*, this module should progress towards achieving this final state and provide related outcomes.

The Social Toolkit module will make use of many types of inputs taken from different sources, such as questionnaires, interviews, online social networks, online blogs, news websites, national and EU legislation, border technologies, real-time as well as historical context-based data etc. These inputs will be aggregated and relevant data will be fed continuously into the simulation model. The socio-cultural framework module (SCFM) and the Automated Threshold Assessment Module (AThAM) modules in section 7.1.2 and 7.1.3, will be serving as subcomponents. More inputs might as well be added from additional sources, such as the ETAP module etc.

Figure 5: Social Toolkit Module

Figure 5 shows the general architecture for developing the METICOS social sensing toolkit (WP6) which will be able to predict technology acceptance for border control technologies from traveller's and border staff's perspective. The toolkit is divided into two stages: 1) agent-based modelling and simulation and 2) social sensing. Stage 1 is all about creating synthetic data for the relevant data categories and manual rules to create first set of simulations reflecting the traveller's as well as border staff's interaction and technology acceptance for border control technologies. Next, the synthetic data and manual rules will be updated with the data from the pilots to include real scenarios and actual technology acceptance rules. The data from pilots will be a controlled data under certain conditions. This stage 1 has the synthetic and controlled data therefore it will only serve as training for the agent-based simulation engine towards predicting the technology acceptance. Stage 2 will use the data and rules information from other sources like online social networks, the web, expected data from BCPs to further enhance the learning/training of the agent-based simulation engine. As this stage has the real data so it will serve as a validation/testing part for the engine to assess its accuracy for predicting technology acceptance. There will be additional information included in form of the questionnaires data regarding traveller's satisfaction from Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) because it is also related to technology acceptance decisions. The social sensing toolkit will use the information from the questionnaire's data to collect technology acceptance related data and rules. Furthermore, the technology acceptance predictions will also serve as an input to technology acceptance decisions.

The main output from simulation runs will be related to the rate of individual agents successfully passing through the border control technology agents. Another important output will be related to the control agents' performance by means of the people reactions to it, in terms of overall satisfaction with the process. If the satisfaction level drops, this may increase the risk of failing to pass another control and thus, the other control agents should adapt to such situation by adjusting the threshold, in connection with the ATHAM module. In the end, the desired outcome should be that all individual agents with acceptable reactions to the technologies should be able to pass through them, while for several others with values near to the threshold, but below, the tool could be able to adjust the latter one or suggest more appropriate technologies or devices that allow them to pass through.

Table 9: Social Toolkit Module Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	NTNU
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	Social Toolkit
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T6.3 - METICOS Social Sensing Toolkit
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	The tool will be developed by NTNU.
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 1 – basic principles observed

Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	The component has been initially proposed during the writing of the proposal. There were different research papers consulted, while there was also an ongoing work related to agent-based simulation and the different data types appropriate for this part of the project.
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	Simulations are used for understanding how a phenomena behaves in a simulated environment. In the METICOS project, the component will be developed in order to discover the underlying connections in the equation(s) between input parameters and outputs in a border crossing point scenario. Examples of outputs are the technology acceptance decision and success rate of the travelers going through the border controls, while inputs are parameters which influence such a decision, as related to the individual context, organizational context etc.. The simulation tool is composed of 2 main sets of agents, representing the travelers and the border control environment with given attributes. There will be further meetings with the relevant stakeholders (border authorities and other technology partners) to support and help the component reach higher readiness levels, towards the desired TRL 5
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	The component will be able to visualize the links between input parameters and the output decisions under the light of simulated data, in the early stages, and then real data collected from border police authorities in the later stages. It will help discover the hidden links between its inputs and outputs and will shed a light on the inner workings of technology acceptance decisions and how that can affect the successful transition of travelers in real time, with given attributes related to attitude, social context and existing laws etc. The component will be able to provide properly aggregated data on the ease of use of the border technologies, the speed of use, more information about the travelers and border authorities (subject to ethical approval), extracted data from social media (in coordination with WP7) etc. Visualisations might include the technology acceptance score and the happiness score of the travelers
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	The main benefit of such a component will be that it will shed a light on the mechanisms that influence technology acceptance decision at border crossing points both from the perspective of travelers and border staff. Such an understanding will help develop technologies which are sufficiently easy, fast and secure

	to use for the average traveler as well as for the border staff.
Data Input Requirements	Individual context (name, age, education, gender etc.), organizational context (laws and rules e.g. data protection and privacy, ethics etc.), behavioral context (e.g. behavioral rules).
Expected Data Output	The output should provide understanding on what the average traveler characteristics on one side are, and the average border technology ones on the other, that would allow him/her to successfully pass the border controls. Data outputs: border technology acceptance score (0-1), travelers ethically approved data on the success/failure cases. These data outputs can be further extended or customized based on how they will be used further, as related to border police, travelers, other technology providers, states etc.
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	We do not expect the necessity of specific hardware interfaces for the purpose of developing a simulation tool.
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	Not known yet (under investigation)
Other Information, Observations, etc.	

Table 10: Social Toolkit Module Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Define input level and values:	Here we will be able to define a list of parameters as appropriate inputs to the tool, along with respective values according to some pre-defined boundaries and other attributes	NTNU	TRL 1 – basic principles observed	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	This is still being under investigation, as main part of the current research plan
Define output level and values:	Here we will be able to define a list of parameters as appropriate inputs to the tool, such as the technology acceptance decision, success rates etc.	NTNU	TRL 1 – basic principles observed	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	This is still being under investigation, main part of the current research plan. Might be same interface with the input level above
Define the mapping level:	Define a proper relation between the input and output parameters - the equation - that will be able to explain and predict the final result	NTNU	TRL 1 – basic principles observed	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	This is still being under investigation, main part of the current research plan. Might be same interface with the levels above

3.6 Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems Module / Interfaces with customs ID system – NET-U

The diagram below shows the 3 components under NetU responsibility i.e.:

- Universal Connector with Modern BCP Risk Assessment Platform
- Interfaces with customs identification systems
- Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems

Included are also the interactions with national, EU and other METICOS services to provide some context.

Figure 6 Interactions with national, EU and other METICOS services

Considering the feedback we received from experts (FRONTEX, EuLisa) it seems that we will not be able to directly connect our system with the existing EU platforms. This means that we need to reconsider and adapt the characteristics of these components accordingly. The components of this list are affected by the aforementioned statement, thus the plan is to include an updated description in deliverable D4.4, in which we will include a detailed analysis of all components of METICOS.

Table 11: Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems Module Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	NET-U
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	Interfaces with Border and Customs Management Information Systems
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	BCMIS
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T8.3
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	Owned by partner
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	TRL 9 – actual system proven in operational environment
Technology/Component History	Various similar systems developed for R&D projects, for the Greek and Cyprus Police, Schengen II database integration
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	The project scope was the design and implementation of the Greek and Cyprus National Schengen Information System II (N.SIS II) and SIRENE System
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	Implementation of all requested and needed interfaces to integrate the various databases of Border and Customs Management Information Systems.
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	Seamless integration of the various databases to support the use cases and act a unique collaboration point beyond the lifecycle of the project.
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	Servers to store the databases and internet connectivity (Ethernet and Wi-Fi).
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	MySQL, Postgress, Oracle databases, REST API, Spring, Docker
Other Information, Observations, etc.	The installation and configuration of servers, network and security equipment, as well as the system software (Databases, Web & Application Servers, Messaging Software, Cluster Software, Backup Software, etc.)

Table 12: Interfaces with Border Management Information Systems Module Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Integration and Interface with Border and Customs Management Information Systems	Development of the data exchange pipelines and Application Programming Interfaces (APIs) with stakeholder information systems following the METICOS services architecture. Special attention has to be given authentication/authorization schemes and on profile-privileges and user rights. Due to the heterogeneity of information and user platforms responsive design methods will be used, utilizing novel cross platform development techniques.	Border Authorities	TRL 7 – system prototype demonstration in operational environment	Must Have	to be defined

3.7 Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data Module – ICCS

The purpose of the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data Module is to process and analyse structured data from various sources in order to uncover the correlations amongst variables of the raw data, regarding the technology acceptance of the Smart Border Control technologies. Examples of the sources which will be the input of this module, include:

- data from the METICOS web-based applications from travelers and border officials,
- questionnaires,
- smileys allowing travelers to provide their feedback regarding their acceptance of the SBC technologies in the pilot sites,
- Social Toolkit module,
- other historical and real-time data from the pilot sites,
- potentially airline data.

Together with the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module (see section 4.6), this module constitutes the Advanced Data Mining Engines. In the figure below, you can see the component’s architecture and the data sources it will process. Moreover, the output of the Advanced Data Mining Engine for Structured Data will be fed in the component Multi-modal Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis Engine, which will be described in section 4.7. Finally, the hidden patterns and the correlations generated by this component will be exposed to the end-user through the DTVA component (section 3.10).

Figure 7 Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data Module

Table 13: Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data Module Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	ICCS
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	NA
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T7.4
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	to be developed by Responsible Partner
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	Elements of the data aggregation and analytics approach that will be employed in the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for structured data have been implemented in fields such as in water management, transport, intelligent mobility etc. in the context of EU-funded projects (such as HARMONY, OPTIMUM, WatERP and others) where ICCS participated as a partner. In addition, the ADME will also use open source libraries (such as Scikit-learn, pandas, numpy, NLTK in Python and more).
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	Although some individual of its elements are already implemented, overall the METICOS ADME for Structured data at the moment is in the stage of Experimental Proof of Concept. We have defined what type of data is needed which need to come from the pilot partners for the pilot BCPs, and we are at the process of defining the pipeline in order to gather, clean and pre-process the data and finally apply BDA algorithms.

<p>Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description</p>	<p>The Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data will process all information relevant to a Border Control Point. This information will consist of large amounts of data coming from several sources (historical data, real-time data gathered at pilot sites, questionnaires ...). The ADME component at the end of the project will uncover hidden patterns amongst attributes of gathered structured data, regarding technology acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies. The user at the end of the project will be able to see these correlations between different attributes of the data with 2d heatmaps, frequency distributions, time series representation of the data in dynamic scale, ranking of categorical variables, outlier/anomaly detection etc. via the DTVA component (developed in task T9.3). Some examples include the impact of waiting time, demographics, total verification time and others on the acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.</p>
<p>Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits</p>	<p>The hidden patterns and the correlations generated by this component will be exposed to the end-user through the DTVA component (see DTVA in section 3.10).</p>
<p>Data Input Requirements</p>	<p>There are 2 sources of data foreseen as input for this component: 1. Existing structured historical and real-time data for each BCP that are defined in the attached Google sheet. 2. Data gathered during the pilot execution through, for example, mobile application for passengers, tablet for officers.. Examples for such data include: demographics of travelers/border guards, questionnaires in order to measure overall acceptance of SBC technologies and individual attributes, smileys... Moreover, as sources of data other METICOS components can be included such as the structured data of the questionnaires from WP5, simulator tool results from WP6.. For more information, see the data layer of the architecture for WP7 in the attached presentation.</p>
<p>Expected Data Output</p>	<p>The expected output, depending of the data available and accessible, would be: - acceptance score, - correlations between different characteristics of the data (for instance how do demographics influence the acceptance of SBC technologies?) - discovery of interesting knowledge and patterns (e.g. are there some technologies which people are more favorable</p>

	towards?)
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	NA
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	NA
Other Information, Observations, etc.	NA

Table 14: Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Structured Data Module Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Generate correlations of structured data from multiple sources	The engine will be able to calculate the correlations between the data available and accessible. The user will be able to see the correlations between different attributes of the data with 2d heatmaps, frequency distributions, time series representation of the data in dynamic scale, ranking of categorical variables, outlier/anomaly detection etc. This visualisation is part of task T9.3 Thus, the user will be able to deduct knowledge on how some characteristics such as demographics, waiting time, overall time to pass the borders, impact the acceptance of SBC technologies.	Data Analyst, Policy maker, Border Authorities	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept	HIGH	service

3.8 Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module – ICCS

The aim of the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module is to gather and analyse unstructured data from different sources. The end goal of the module is to uncover the hidden patterns amongst variables of the raw data, concerning the technology and societal acceptance of the Smart Border Control technologies. Indicative data sources which will be used as input of this module are the following:

- social media data (Twitter, online reviews...)
- free text in questionnaires,
- historical and real-time unstructured data from the pilot sites.

In the figure below, you can see this individual component’s architecture together with its inputs. The output of the Advanced Data Mining Engine for Unstructured Data will be fed in the component Multi-modal Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis Engine, which will be described in section 4.7. Finally, the hidden patterns and the correlations generated by this component will be exposed to the end-user through the DTVA component (section 3.10).

Figure 8 Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module

Table 15: Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	ICCS
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data

Technology/Component Other Internal Name	NA
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T7.3
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	to be developed by Responsible Partner
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	Elements of the data aggregation and analytics approach that will be employed in the Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data have been implemented in fields such as in water management, transport, intelligent mobility etc. in the context of EU-funded projects (such as HARMONY, OPTIMUM, WatERP and others) where ICCS participated as a partner. In addition, the ADME will also use opensource libraries (such as Scikit-learn, pandas, numpy, NLTK in Python).
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	Although some individual of its elements are already implemented, overall the METICOS ADME at the moment is in the stage of Experimental Proof of Concept. ADME for unstructured data is currently collecting is Twitter data and online reviews which can be used to infer the acceptance of various SBC technologies and we have created a pipeline in order to pre-process, clean and apply Big Data Analytics algorithms to the crawled data.
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	The Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for unstructured data will process all unstructured data relevant to a Border Control Point. This information will consist of large amounts of data coming from several sources (historical unstructured data, real-time unstructured, data gathered at pilot sites, free text in questionnaires, tweets and social media data related to BCPs ...). The ADME component at the end of the project will uncover hidden patterns amongst attributes of gathered data, regarding technology acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies. The user at the end of the project will be able to see these correlations between different attributes of the data with 2d heatmaps, frequency distributions, clustering, most

	important words through wordclouds, outlier/anomaly detection etc., via the DTVA component, developed in task T9.3. Some examples include the impact of waiting time, demographics, total verification time and others, deducted from the unstructured data, on the acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies.
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	The hidden patterns and the correlations generated by this component will be exposed to the end-user through the DTVA component (see DTVA section 3.10).
Data Input Requirements	As the input data, we define mainly 1. tweets and in general social media data, 2. the data gathered during the pilot execution through, for example, mobile application for passengers, tablet for officers.. Examples for such data include: free text in questionnaires in order to measure overall acceptance of SBC technologies and individual attributes, tweets, ... Moreover, as sources of data other METICOS components can be included such as the unstructured data from questionnaires from WP5 (e.g. free text), simulator tool results (unstructured data output - e.g.text..) from WP6.. For more information, see the data layer of the architecture for WP7 in the attached presentation.
Expected Data Output	The expected output, depending of the data available and accessible, would be: - acceptance score, - correlations between different characteristics of the data - discovery of interesting knowledge and patterns (e.g. are there some technologies which people are more favorable towards?)
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	NA
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	NA
Other Information, Observations, etc.	NA

Table 16: Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Extract data from social media	The engine will be capable of extracting data from social media (twitter, reviews, blogs...) in a real-time automated way and storing it with the aim of further processing the data.	Data Analyst, Border Authorities	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept	HIGH	service
Detect sentiment and context from data	The engine will include the functionality of sentiment detection and context detection (most important words, clustering..) of social media data (twitter, reviews, blogs..) in order to capture the general acceptance and social acceptance of SBC technologies. The user will be able to see most important words, the context where these are used, clusters of the main subjects that people are tweeting about regarding smart border control technologies and the BCP...	Policy Maker, Data Analyst, Border Authorities	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept	HIGH	service
Generate correlations of data from multiple sources	The engine will be able to calculate the correlations between the unstructured data. This data includes social media data, real-time data from pilot execution (questionnaires, tweets...), free text from the questionnaires from WP6, outputs from simulation engine from WP7.... The user will be able to see the correlations between different attributes of the data with 2d heatmaps, frequency distributions, time series representation of the data in dynamic scale, ranking of categorical variables, outlier/anomaly detection etc. This visualisation is part of task T9.3 (component DTVA).	Data Analyst, Policy maker, Border Authorities	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept	MEDIUM	service

3.9 Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis mechanisms Module – ICCS

The purpose of the Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis Mechanisms module is to infer the acceptance of a BCP or technology by aggregating and analyzing data from different sources, locations and formats. It accepts as input the aforementioned data as well as the outputs of other components (ADME for Structured data, ADME for Unstructured data, and others). The output of the CS-BDA component will be fed in the DTVA component, which is described in section 3.10.

Figure 9 Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis Mechanisms module

Table 17: Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis mechanisms Module Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	ICCS
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis mechanisms
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	Multi-modal Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis mechanisms
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T7.5
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	to be developed by Responsible Partner
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 2 – technology concept formulated

Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	Elements of the approach that will be employed in the Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis mechanisms have been implemented in fields such as in transport, intelligent mobility etc. in the context of EU-funded projects (such as HARMONY, OPTIMUM, and others) where ICCS participated as a partner.
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	The Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analytics mechanisms component is currently at the TRL 2, which means that the technology concept is formulated. This module aims to aggregate the data from different sources, locations and formats with the aim of deducing the overall acceptance score and understanding the acceptance of different technologies corresponding to different criteria.
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	The Cross-Sectorial (Big) Data Analysis Mechanisms module aims to analyze and aggregate data from different sources, locations and formats. This will be achieved by being the centralizing point of the output of other components (ADME for Structured data, ADME for Unstructured data). The output of CS-BDA component will be fed in the DTVA component (visualisation component - GUI addressed to end-users). For more information, please see the attached WP7 architecture.
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	The output of this component will be exposed to the end-user through the DTVA component (see DTVA in section 3.10).
Data Input Requirements	For the SC-BDA component, as data inputs we define the output of the following components: ADME for Structured data and ADME for Unstructured Data.
Expected Data Output	The expected output will be fed in the visualisation METICOS component - DTVA. The expected outputs are: 1. the aggregated acceptance from structured and unstructured data and 2. the predictive functions of the acceptance of SBC technologies in a new BCP based on the data gathered and analyzed from existing ones (for which the data is available and accessible).
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	NA
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	NA
Other Information, Observations, etc.	NA

Table 18: Advanced Data Mining Engine (ADME) for Unstructured Data Module Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Aggregate multi-modal data from other METICOS components	Building upon the results of each dataset (incl. data sources providing structured & unstructured data, output from other METICOS components), the user can view the overall acceptance score for all BCPs and understand better the acceptance based on different criteria.	Border Guard, Border Police, Data Analyst, Policy maker	TRL 2 – technology concept formulated	MEDIUM	service
Predict acceptance	The user will be able to predict the acceptance of the SBC technologies of a "new" BCP (a BCP for which no analysis has been conducted) based on available data from other BCPs. (<i>cross-sector analysis of acceptance</i>)	Border Guard, Border Police, Data Analyst, Policy maker	TRL 2 – technology concept formulated	LOW	service

3.10 Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module – ICCS

The aim of the Interactive Visual Analytics Technologies component is to provide a platform for the end-users to view, explore and analyse correlations of data generated from other METICOS components (for instance the Social Toolkit module and the Embedded Technology Acceptance Prediction module) as well as the data gathered during the pilots, related to technology acceptance and efficiency of Smart Border Control Technologies. It will provide a platform where the outputs from the ADME for Structured Data, ADME for Unstructured Data and CS-BDA modules will be visualised and presented. Last but not least, the DTVA module will allow the interested stakeholders to import data so that they can easily discover new insights using self-service analytics. Below, you can find the architecture of this component in relation to the other METICOS components:

Figure 10 Architecture of the Data, Text and Visual Analytics component

Table 19: Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	ICCS
--	------

Technology/Component Name within METICOS	Data, Text and Visual Analytics
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	DTVA
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T9.3
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	to be developed by Responsible Partner
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 2 – technology concept formulated
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	TRL 6 – technology demonstrated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	Elements of the data visualisation approach that will be employed in the Interactive Visual Analytics Technologies have been implemented in fields such as sustainable water management and others in the context of EU-funded projects (such as NAIADES) where ICCS participated as a partner.
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	DTVA at the moment is in the stage of Experimental Proof of Concept. DTVA will offer reporting and visualisation capabilities. Some examples include correlations between different attributes of the unstructured data with 2d heatmaps, frequency distributions, context analysis of twitter data, most important words using wordclouds, time series representation of structured data and much more. For more detailed information, see the attached presentation.
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	The Interactive Visual Analytics Technologies component at the end of the project will provide a platform for the end-users to view, explore and analyze correlations from the data in previous WPs as well as the data gathered during the pilots, and uncover hidden patterns amongst them, related to technology acceptance of Smart Border Control Technologies. It will provide a platform where the outputs from the ADME for Structured Data, ADME for Unstructured Data and CS-BDA modules will be visualized and presented to the end users. The goal of this module is to visualize, analyze and explore also the data obtained from WP5 and WP6. This module will provide access to the data analysis algorithms in order to execute them interactively.

Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	<p>The users at the end of the project will have multiple benefits, including :</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. they will gain a better understanding of the social acceptance from data gathered at pilot sites (historical and real-time) regarding Smart Border Control technologies, by viewing correlations between the data .Some examples of these correlations are: <i>Does waiting time play a part in how travelers assess the SBC technologies?, Does weather have an impact in the acceptance of SBC technologies for the case of land borders? How important is the total verification time of individual SBC technologies in their acceptance?</i> 2. Users will discover hidden patterns between data related to the acceptance of SBC technologies, 3. They will extract knowledge on the correlations, and thus insight to possible causal relationships, between the described features and dependent/target variable (acceptance of SBC technologies) 4. They will be presented with live twitter feed from the BCP of interest 5. They are able to perform more in depth analysis by generating correlations in existing and also new datasets (self-management concept) 6. They are able to understand the context and the overall acceptance of SBC technologies as this is expressed in social media.
Data Input Requirements	<p>The data needed for this module is the data which will be depicted in the architecture in the attached presentation. That means, output from ADME for Structured data, ADME for Unstructured data and CS-BDA (<i>also potentially output from TAM and relevant questionnaires used in that scope as well as the data simulation tool from WP6</i>)</p>
Expected Data Output	<p>Visualisation of output data from other modules, which are mentioned above</p>
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	<p>NA</p>
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	<p>NA</p>
Other Information, Observations, etc.	<p>NA</p>

Table 20: Data, Text and Visual Analytics Module Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Visualize correlations of data from multiple sources	The user will have a view of the visual output produced in other modules, namely ADME for Structured data, ADME for Unstructured data and CS-BDA . Some examples include social media context analysis (most important words, clustering...), time series of waiting time, acceptance score... More information can be found in each respective component. Moreover, the user will be able to see a live feed of twitter streams for the BCP of their interest.	Border Guard, Border Police, Data Analyst, Policy maker	TRL 2 – technology concept formulated	HIGH	service
Produce further analysis of existing and new data	The user can explore the data and their correlations in more detail, by for example, changing some parameters, or selecting part of it and viewing some of its characteristics in more detail. Furthermore, the user will be able to import new datasets, create new correlations between new and/or existing data, and perform further in-depth analysis.	Border Guard, Border Police, Data Analyst, Policy maker	TRL 2 – technology concept formulated	MEDIUM	service

3.11 METICOS Middleware Module – MAGG

The METICOS middleware module aims at creating adaptors for accumulating and aggregating information from a number of mobile terminals and cameras (hard real-time data), and law enforcement/border authorities information systems. To this end, it uses Web Services, a standardized medium to propagate communication between the client and server applications, by providing a common platform that allows multiple applications built on various programming languages to have the ability to communicate with each other. Web Services encompass a set of related application functions that can be dynamically deployed to perform complex transactions in real time with minimal human interaction. Their main advantages over other architectures is that they are modular and easily expandable, in the sense that simple services can be easily aggregated to form more complex ones; self contained and platform-independent, given that they are based on a concise set of open, XML based standards designed to promote interoperability across a variety of platforms; and self describing, meaning that both the client and the server need to recognize only the format and content of request and response messages without the need for any external metadata repositories or code generation tools.

The METICOS middleware module will leverage a RESTful Web Services architecture. Representational state transfer (REST) is a software architectural style that defines a set of constraints to be used for creating Web services. Web services that conform to the REST architectural style, provide interoperability between computer systems on the Web and allow the requesting systems to access and manipulate textual representations of Web resources by using a uniform and predefined set of stateless operations.

All information coming from various data sources (surveys, «smileys», cameras e.t.c) will be sent to the middleware module for processing and/or storage. That information will be used to perform data mining and analytics about the passengers' perception of the technologies used at border checkpoints. For this process, various law enforcement information systems may also be utilized to provide additional information about passenger statistics. The law enforcement information systems may also be used by the border authorities to collect additional information about passengers. The communications of all channels will be encrypted and the privacy of the users will be ensured for the purposes of determining their acceptance of border technologies.

Figure 11 Architecture of the METICOS middleware component

Table 21: METICOS Middleware Module Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	MAGGIOLI
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	METICOS Middleware
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	MM
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T8.2
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	Owned by partner
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	For the middleware development partner MAG will capitalise on the knowledge acquired from the running projects FactLog SPIRE project (2019-2023) and AquaSpice (2020-2024) projects. In these projects MAG is responsible for the development of the middleware / message bus with security services allowing exchange of information among systems. The target TRL for the message bus / middleware component in both FactLog

	and AquaSpice is TRL6.
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	<p>Software middleware that returns information about a requested passenger, given a unique key (e.g Passport Number), provides additional information through sensors and information aggregation/mining capabilities.</p> <p>Security layer for authentication, encryption and privacy for transmission of sensitive, personal data and sensors (e.g. cameras, iris scanners).</p>
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	<p>METICOS middleware will be a software system that will facilitate data communication between identification equipment, such as biometric sensors, risk management methods and border authorities and law enforcement information systems.</p> <p>Implementation of secure data transmission between components of middleware.</p>
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	<p>Robust management information system for heterogeneous data sources, including an API and integrated GW capabilities. Able to virtualise all information. Guarantee security control for users, exchange information and privacy of information for all data sources.</p> <p>Protection of sensitive data.</p>
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	Wifi, Ethernet, Sensor's hardware
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	API, REST, Spring, Swagger-UI, Docker, Proprietary sensor interfaces
Other Information, Observations, etc.	Partners should provide access to the needed sensors / sensor data.

Table 22: METICOS Middleware Module Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Return Passenger Information upon request	METICOS middleware will be a software system that will facilitate data communication between identification equipment, such as biometric sensors, risk management methods and border authorities and law enforcement information systems.	Border Authorities	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	Must Have	
Event Filtering	Filtering of information coming in from sensors for the purpose of facilitating the storage and handling of heterogeneous data.	Border Authorities	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	Must Have	
Information Aggregation, Storage, mining	Aggregation of data for purposes of statistical analysis and for discovery of patterns within the data set.	Border Authorities	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	Must Have	
Authentication	Security layer for authentication of users accessing the system	Border Authorities	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	Must Have	
Encryption	Encryption and privacy for transmission of sensitive, personal data and sensors (e.g. cameras, iris scanners).	Border Authorities	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	Must Have	

3.12 Smart Front-End Infrastructure Module – MAGG

Personnel Front-End

In order to protect access to the information in the METICOS system to authorized personnel, METICOS implements role based security where user identity is verified. After the operator logs in to the system, the Dashboard screen is displayed as the main view showing a map of the border checkpoints with control points, sensors, and alarms. Its purpose is to let the user to gain situational awareness about available resources, latest risk alerts, traffic graphs at border checkpoints and the analytics tools.

This module provides an aggregated view of the various visualizations and analytics provided by other modules of the METICOS project. All analytics about the acceptance of border checkpoint technology will be displayed here in various formats. Some of those metrics might include star ratings over time, speed, ease of use, emotional response. They will be displayed using graphs, pie charts and histograms that span a certain time period that may be selected by the user. The user will also have the ability to view analytics for specific checkpoints as well as aggregated analytics for all checkpoints.

Border Checkpoint and Mobile App for passengers

The passengers will be able to see the airport's latest news, information about their flights and airport facilities, give reactions (e.g. smileys, star ratings), answer questionnaires and provide feedback through passenger kiosks placed at border checkpoints. These functionalities can also be accessed from the passengers' personal devices by downloading a mobile application to their cellphone or tablet. This application also enables use of the platform by people with disabilities through the use of audio based on WCAG 2.0 (Web Content Accessibility Guidelines).

Figure 12 Smart Front-End

Table 23: Smart Front-End Infrastructure Module Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	MAGGIOLI
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	Front End
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	FE
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T8.5
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	Owned by partner
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	Already existing R&D projects
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	Implementation of Front End platform for visualisation of data fusion intended for border authorities.
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	Easy to operate and descriptive platform.
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	Ease of access to data from multiple components, facilitating the operations of border authorities.
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	Ethernet and Wifi
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	VueJS, REST, Spring, Docker
Other Information, Observations, etc.	End users should provide their comments on the functionality and ease of use of the system.

Table 24: Smart Front-End Infrastructure Module Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Front End	Implementation of Front End platform for visualisation of data fusion intended for border authorities.	Border Authorities	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	Must Have	

3.13 Universal Connector with Modern BCP Risk Assessment Platform – SIMAVI

Table 25: Universal Connector with Modern BCP Risk Assessment Platform Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	SIMAVI
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	Universal Connector with Modern BCP Risk Assessment Platform
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	UC
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T9.2
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	owned by partner
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment
Technology/Component History	Previous R&D projects, internal projects
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	The component offers a uniform access to various data sources. It offers a standard API to access data from different data sources and hides their technological implementation details. The component has multiple connector modules that support various connection types. These types may be (but not limited to) REST implementation of a web service, to gather data from multiple data sources, where a web service is concerned.
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	UC component will act as an extended connection pooling mechanism with automated selection of connection type and data source. Each connection type and data source will have to have its own security system implemented, with an automated management interface implemented.
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reduces the number of times new connection objects are created. - Promotes connection object reuse. - Quickens the process of getting a connection. - Reduces the amount of effort required to manually manage connection objects. - Minimizes the number of stale connections. - Controls the amount of resources spent on maintaining connections.
Data Input Requirements	N/A (the component can handle the data formats of supported connection types)
Expected Data Output	N/A (the data from the source system is return to the caller)
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	Ethernet
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	REST, SQL
Other Information, Observations, etc.	N/A

Table 26: Universal Connector with Modern BCP Risk Assessment Platform Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Generic implementation for all connector types to data sources. Interfaces with customs identification systems	UC will act as an extended connection pooling mechanism with automated selection of connection type and data source. Each connection type and data source will have to have its own security system implemented, with an automated management interface implemented.	N/A	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept	TRL 5 – technology validated in relevant environment	The methods depend on the data sources supported. No specific data structure, this depends on the data sources supported.

3.14 Data Integration Module – SIMAVI

Table 27: Data Integration Module Description

Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	SIMAVI
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	METICOS Common Data Management Engine
Technology/Component Other Internal Name	CDME
Corresponding Task in METICOS	T4.5, T9.2
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	owned by partner
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	TRL 8 – system complete and qualified
Technology/Component History	Previous R&D projects, internal projects
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	The component is able to store structured and unstructured data from various heterogeneous sources. It is suitable to be used with both static or real time data.
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	CDME will be a model aiming to unify the representation of data originating from multiple heterogeneous sources and encoded in multiple diverse formats, in order to facilitate data storage and retrieval, as well as to support the interconnection and communication of diverse components of a system. The information will be organized using hierarchical data models, which will facilitate not only the data minimization procedure, but also the scalable hierarchical analysis approach that will be followed by the existing partners' analytics infrastructure (see Section 1) for application on Big Data
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	Uniform data access for all the components, history of actions, better security.
Data Input Requirements	Static or real time, structured or unstructured data from BCP or other METICOS components
Expected Data Output	The data is stored in hierarchical format (HDF) and will be accessible to METICOS components
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	Ethernet, storage
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	HDF
Other Information, Observations, etc.	N/A

Table 28: Data Integration Module Capabilities

Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
<p>Storing the static and the real-time dynamic information acquired from various heterogeneous sources in the METICOS Ecosystem in a uniform way</p>	<p>METICOS Common Data Management Engine (CDME) is responsible for storing the static and the real-time dynamic information acquired from various heterogeneous sources in the METICOS Ecosystem in a uniform way. All the exchanged information will be translated and presented in an understandable form, so as all METICOS components use them. It will contain information about the METICOS Ecosystem static information such as building architectural map, actors, procedures, equipment related to the project, installed sensors that will be used, etc. Furthermore, it will include the dynamic aspects related to the METICOS Ecosystem, including events and context information (e.g. location, time, etc.), alerts, measurements, events related to re-adaptation and training activities and social platform, etc.</p>	<p>N/A</p>	<p>TRL 3 – experimental proof of concept</p>	<p>TRL 8 – system complete and qualified</p>	<p>Input: structured or unstructured data, static or dynamic data from BCP and other METICOS components</p> <p>Output: the data stored is translated to a common vocabulary and can be retrieved by METICOS components</p>

3.15 Data Privacy Schemes – MAGG

The component responsible for the authentication, encryption and privacy of sensitive, personal data and sensor data is the “METICOS Middleware Module”. There is no separate “Data privacy schemes” component. The description of the “METICOS Middleware Module” module has been included in the Technologies and Capabilities excel file and considered in the architecture high level diagram

4 User requirements

This Chapter represents the main output of the first iteration cycle of T4.1. In other words, it presents the first iteration of the user role definitions and user requirements. As explained in Section 2.2 a variety of instruments for data collection, analysis and collaboration were used to arrive at this first formulation of user roles and user requirements.

4.1 User role definitions

These potential user roles identified in this chapter are based on the Preliminary Questionnaire for End User Partners Specifically questions 6 and 7 of the questionnaire addressed these issues:

5. Please describe the categories of people that you envisage the METICOS project to measure their acceptance of the Smart Border technologies.

Some categories may include:

- *Travelers: passengers (Third Country Nationals, EU-citizens)*
- *Operational staff: border guards, customs, police authorities, immigration services...*
- *Other: civil society, data privacy experts, ethics and human rights experts...*

Police Boarder Control Officers and Immigration Officers working at the airports.

6. Please mention **other stakeholders**, apart from your authority/organization, which would need access to the social acceptance and impact that we will measure and are potential future users of the METICOS solution.

Some examples may include:

- *Operational: border guards, customs, police authorities, immigration services...*
- *Policy: EU Parliament, EC, EU Council, National policy makers...*

Technical: ABC systems and equipment manufacturers & responsible for maintenance of these systems...

Based on the answers primarily to Q5 but also to some extent to Q6, a set of 12 potential user roles were identified as presented in Table 29 below.

Table 29: User role by end-user organization

Name	Short name	Type of border	Operational				Policy			Technical	Management		Other	
			Border guards	Immigration Officers	Customs officers	Police authorities	National Policy Makers	Data privacy expert	Ethics and human rights expert	Responsible for maintenance of systems	Chief	Deputy chief	Cadet	Traveller
Cyprus police	CYPOL	Air border	X	X		X								X
Politsei- ja Piirivalveamet	PPA	Sea border	X	X	X	X		X	X				X	X
YPIRESIA DIACHEIRISIS EUROPAIKON KAI ANAPTYXIAKON PROGRAMMATON	MoCP/E DPD	Air border	X		X	X								X
INSPECTORATUL TERITORIAL AL POLITIEI DE FRONTIERA TIMISOARA	ITPFT	Land border	X	X	X	X	X			X	X	X		X

4.2 User requirements

This section presents the first results of our user requirements elicitation and analysis. As stipulated in the DOA, it presents the first iteration of user requirements out of three iteration cycles. We identified a number of 9 functional requirements and 4 non-functional requirements.

Table 30: User requirements

UR_CODE	Name	End-User interest			
		CYPOL	MoCP/EDPD	PPA	ITPFT
UFR_1	Detect correlations/patterns in large amounts of data	3 - Very important	3 - Very Important	3 - Very important	2 - Important
UFR_2	Fill in questionnaires	3 - Very important	2 - Important	2 - Important	1 - Somewhat important
UFR_3	Configure System and Components	1 - Somewhat important	1 - Somewhat important	3 - Very important	2 - Important
UFR_4	View models of and predict technology acceptance	1 - Somewhat important	2 - Important	2 - Important	2 - Important
UFR_5	Define and predict thresholds of acceptance of technologies	1 - Somewhat important	2 - Important	2 – Important	3 - Very important
UFR_6	Predictive analytics and decision support	-	3 - Very important	3 - Very important	3 - Very important
UFR_7	Continuous monitoring of technology acceptance	2 - Important	3 - Very important	2 - Important	2 - Important
UFR_8	Simulation of individuals and technologies	2 - Important	3 - Very important	2 - Important	2 - Important

UFR_93	Assessment of Risk Profiling Technologies ³	3 - Very important	3 - Very important	3 - Very important	3 - Very important
UNFR_1	Future Proofing	1 - Somewhat important	3 - Very important	2 - Important	2 - Important
UNFR_2	User Friendliness	3 - Very important	2 - Important	3 - Very important	3 - Very important
UNFR_3	Security	3 - Very important	3 - Very important	3 - Very important	3 - Very important
UNFR_4	Privacy	3 - Very important	3 - Very important	3 - Very important	3 - Very important

³ Discussions are under way within the consortium as to whether this requirement is feasible under the project. For the moment this has been included in the list of requirements. A final decision will be made by M12 whether this requirement will remain within the scope of feasible requirements.

4.2.1 Functional requirements

UR_CODE	UFR_1
Name	Detect correlations/patterns in large amounts of data
Description	The METICOS System shall process/analyze large amounts of structured and unstructured data (historical, real time data gathered at border points, questionnaire data, etc.), that is relevant at Border Control Points and uncover hidden patterns/correlations among the data.
Justification and comments	<p>The user will be able to see these correlations between different attributes of the data with 2d heatmaps, frequency distributions, time series representation of the data in dynamic scale, ranking of categorical variables, outlier/anomaly detection etc.</p> <p>The user will be able to deduct knowledge on how some characteristics such as demographics, waiting time, overall time to pass the borders, impact the acceptance of SBC technologies.</p> <p>The user will be able to see most important words, the context where these are used, clusters of the main subjects that people are tweeting about regarding smart border control technologies and the BCP.</p>

UR_CODE	UFR_2
Name	Fill in questionnaires
Description	The METICOS System shall allow users to fill in questionnaires (primarily by means of tablets or monitors of ABC systems) as data inputs for the System.
Justification and comments	The user will be able to fill in questionnaires.

UR_CODE	UFR_3
Name	Configure System and Components
Description	The METICOS System shall allow users to configure the System and its components.
Justification and comments	The user will be able to configure the System and its components.
DoA Support	<p>Description of the action (part A).pdf (page 39)</p> <p>"Specification of the interfaces and interactions needed in order to enable travellers and competent authorities/staff to access, handle, monitor and configure METICOS services"</p>

UR_CODE	UFR_4
Name	View models of and predict technology acceptance

Description	The METICOS System shall analyze data about border crossing technologies acceptance producing models predicting the likelihood of acceptance/non-acceptance by a given group (travelers, Border Authority). Such models shall be based on metrics/variables/KPIs such as: user’s behavioral intention of future use (of BCTs), user’s satisfaction, performance expectancy (or perceived usefulness), effort expectancy (or ease of use), technology anxiety, facilitating conditions, privacy, ethical and societal perceptions, etc.
Justification and comments	The user will be able to view models of and predict technology acceptance. It will see dashboard widgets that are used to display numerical values representing acceptance related factors based on the calculations of the ETAP module. Also, an admin user is able to change several parameters of the underlying ETAP module to evaluate how acceptance is affected if e.g. demographic aspects of travellers are changed.

UR_CODE	UFR_5
Name	Define and predict thresholds of acceptance of technologies
Description	The METICOS System shall define and predict (based on various data/parameters) thresholds of acceptance of different border crossing technologies.
Justification and comments	We will define and predict thresholds of acceptable technologies. Automated tools for assessing threshold are multiagent based tools such as Netlogo, Gama, GlobalSimulate etc.

UR_CODE	UFR_6
Name	Predictive analytics and decision support
Description	The METICOS System shall provide predictive analytics (including “nowcasting”) and decision support functionalities for Border Crossing Authorities to aid efficiency and acceptance improvement of border crossing technologies.
Justification and comments	The user can explore the data and their correlations in more detail, by for example, changing some parameters, or selecting part of it and viewing some of its characteristics in more detail. Furthermore, the user will be able to import new datasets, create new correlations between new and/or existing data, and perform further in-depth analysis.

UR_CODE	UFR_7
Name	Continuous monitoring of technology acceptance
Description	The METICOS System shall provide continuous monitoring of the technology acceptance considering the different behavioral patterns of people and the interactions between them trying to pass the EU border control systems trying to use the modern border control technologies.

Justification and comments	The future meetings and the datasets from the border authorities will help us validate the simulation tool and use it to predict technology acceptance levels of border crossing technologies continuously. Such monitoring will help in 1) assessing the maturity levels of the border crossing technologies for meeting the needs of traveller and border crossing point staff and hence going beyond the EU's border control systems. 2) support stakeholders with decision making related to which technologies to install at the borders 3) understanding the underlying factors and processes related to border technology acceptance 4) supporting stakeholders and technology providers with making decisions related to technology designs and actual technology needs.
----------------------------	--

UR_CODE	UFR_8
Name	Simulation of individuals and technologies
Description	The METICOS System shall allow (multi agent) simulation of individuals with given sets of attributes against a specific BCP technology with its attributes, within a given country or system as part of a possible scenario.
Justification and comments	The simulation tool is composed of 2 main sets of agents, representing the travellers and the border control environment with given attributes.

UR_CODE	UFR_9 ³
Name	Assessment of Risk Profiling Technologies3
Description	The METICOS System should assess the acceptance of already existing Risk Profiling Technologies.
Justification and comments	The user will be able to view the acceptance of Risk Profiling Technologies.

4.2.2 Non-Functional requirements

UR_CODE	UNFR_1
Name	Future Proofing
Description	The METICOS System shall be able to be improved with the future addition of new data and data sources.

UR_CODE	UNFR_2
Name	User Friendliness
Description	The METICOS System shall present data in a comprehensive, user-friendly and intuitive manner for users.

UR_CODE	UNFR_3
Name	Security

Description	The METICOS System shall implement secure data transmission between its components and between itself and other systems (such as Border Authorities' Systems, etc.). A security layer for authentication, encryption and privacy for transmission of sensitive data (including personal data) shall be implemented.
-------------	---

UR_CODE	UNFR_4
Name	Privacy
Description	The METICOS System shall be implemented in line with privacy legal regulations and ethical standards at EU and relevant national levels.

5 Conclusions

The main objective of this deliverable was to identify the user roles and formalize a list of user requirements for the METICOS System. To arrive at this goal we relied on a cooperative or co-design approach bringing together all members of the consortium in their various capacities. We employed a variety of methods and activities: questionnaires, regular and ad-hoc meetings, formal workshops, etc.

On our way to identifying user requirements we have also created in Chapter 3 a Catalogue of Technologies and Capabilities. While this was not explicitly required by the DOA, we believed it was necessary in order to have a good description of the components and their capabilities that would serve both the main goal of this deliverable as well as later work under at least T4.1, T4.3 and T4.4.

This deliverable achieved its aim of defining a first iteration list of user requirements for the METICOS System, in Chapter 3.15. We see this as a first iteration that will needs but also enables further work. One of the conclusions of work to define user requirements was that there is a mutual need of information from Technological Partners to End User Partners and vice-versa, that requires several iterations in order to arrive at an optimal level of detail of requirements. On the one hand, technological partners needed to understand what data are available on the side of End User organizations in order to formulate more exactly what functionalities could be offered by their components. On the other hand, End Users needed to understand more exactly what functionalities are possible in order to express their requirements.

The activities we organized thus far under T/D4.1 allowed us to provide this first list of deliverables. However, as we are finalizing this deliverable we have planned next activities under this Task4.1 to allow us to define technical/system specifications and possibly provide another iteration of user requirements.

References

- Carroll, J.M., 2004. Participatory Design of Community Information Systems: The Designer as Bard, in: Darses, F., Dieng, R., Simone, C., Zacklad, M. (Eds.), *Cooperative Systems Design: Scenario Based Design of Collaborative Systems*, *Frontiers in Artificial Intelligence and Applications*. IOS Press, Amsterdam, pp. 1–7.
- Greenbaum, J., Kyng, M., 1991. Introduction: Situated Design, in: *Design at Work: Cooperative Design of Computer Systems*. Lawrence Erlbaum Associates, Hillsdale, NJ, pp. 1–24.
- Steen, M., Manschot, M., Koning, N.D., 2011. Benefits of Co-design in Service Design Projects. *Int. J. Des. 5*, 53–60.
- Wieggers, K., Beatty, J., 2013. *Software Requirements*, 3rd ed. Microsoft Press, Redmond, WA, USA.

APPENDIX I: Replies to the questionnaire

Cyprus police

1. Please specify the **Border Control Point(s) (BCP)** that the pilot will take place.

For each BCP, we would like to know:

- *the exact location*
- *the type of border (air, land, sea...)*
- *traffic mix (for instance for land borders, people crossing border on foot, personal vehicles, public transport, cargo vehicles...)*
- *traffic (how many crossings per day)*
- *any relevant information regarding the pilot location (challenges the border guards and authorities have to face...)*

The pilot will take place at the Larnaka International Airport i.e. air border.

Air traffic consists of cargo and passengers.

To provide information on the traffic, we selected one day (12/7/2019) which is representative of the traffic that occurs during high season. During that day, 37,238 passengers crossed the border, out of which 14,441 (6,931 arrivals and 7,510 departures) used the borderXpress kiosks (see below).

2. Please describe the **process(es)** that are being used at the Border Control Point. Please include no-gate control technologies and manual operations (if they are still being used), for which you want to measure the social acceptance.

Make sure to include:

- *what **technologies** are being used. For instance, if an Automated Border Control (ABC) gate is in use, specify if it is integrated with the processes or standalone, if there are one or two steps in the process of the border control passage etc. Please make sure to include if a pre-border check is currently operational (use of kiosks)*
- *what **raw data** are being gathered to measure the performance of the process*
- *availability of the above **data grouped** by demographics (age group, nationality, level of education...)*
- *the type of biometrics being used (Facial Image (FI), Fingerprints (FP) & how many, Iris) and at which process(es)/stage(s) of the process each (pre-enrolment, authentication and verification, border passage entry/exit ...)*

At the arrivals and departures area of the two International Airports, interactive borderXpress kiosks are deployed within the restricted area close to the passport control booths, so that passengers can perform self-check. Currently (and since July 2018), 74 borderXpress kiosks are operating at both airports as follows:

Air border

- Larnaka Airport: 44 kiosks (26 at Arrivals and 18 at Departures),
- Pafos Airport: 34 kiosks (18 at Arrivals and 12 at Departures).

Developed more than 10 years ago by ITS, the team at Vancouver International Airport (YVR) tasked with developing innovative solutions to improve passenger experiences, borderXpress is a solution that uses self-service biometric-enabled kiosks to expedite the border control process.

When the arriving and departing passengers approach Arrivals or Departures Terminals respectively, the staff of the airport operator, directs the passengers who can benefit from the use of the kiosks, towards them, while the rest of the passengers are directed towards the passport control booths in order to undergo the traditional border check.

At the area of the borderXpress kiosks, 1 dedicated employee of the airport operator is responsible for every 4 kiosks, undertaking the task to assist passengers who are not familiar with the process, to perform the self-service passport control.

After passengers select their preferred language from a variety of up to 35 available languages, they scan their travel document, and take a face photo. Then, the photo is compared to the photo stored in the document chip for verification. Additionally, certain security checks are carried out in order to verify the validity of the document. At the end, the personal data of the passengers as well as the presented documents are checked against the national database and against the Interpol's Stolen and Lost Documents Database (SLTD).

After concluding the above checks, a token is issued for each passenger which contains the photo taken at the kiosk, their personal data, a password which changes regularly for security reasons, the coded results of the face recognition comparison checks and security checks of the document and possible hits in the available databases.

After the self-check, passengers are then directed to the border guards who are dedicated to the check of the passengers who used the borderXpress kiosks. According to the passenger traffic, one or more border guards are assigned to this task. The border guards receive the "clear" tokens, i.e. the tokens which indicate that passengers and their document successfully passed all checks and there is not any hit in the available databases. One or more dedicated border guards receive the "no clear" tokens, i.e. the rejected ones. Passengers without any hit, cross the border and continue to their destination while the rest is directed to manual check carried out by border guards, according to the result of the issued token and the national and European legislation.

The border guard scans the document of the passenger on the full page integrated passport reader (MRZ) and carries out a thorough check following the traditional border check process. If needed, the passengers are directed to the second line office for additional checks or other actions.

The borderXpress kiosks are completely configurable and can be adapted to meet each country's requirements. The coded indications can be defined by the local authorities, based on the European / National Legislation of the country, such as: warrants of arrest, discreet check / monitoring, special check / monitoring, obligation for military service, minor passenger, stolen / lost travel document, failure in face recognition, failure in one or more document authenticity checks, etc.

As already mentioned above, the borderXpress kiosk are not equipped with any kind of barriers to control and monitor the number of passengers who have been granted access or rejected, since the final decision is always made by the dedicated border guard.

It is also worth to mention that, according to a Police Protocol, all issued tokens are collected by the border guard who is responsible to check them and are handed over, regularly, to the person who is in charge of the specific Terminal (Group leader), usually a senior police constable or a sergeant. After a certain period of time, which is set at 3 hours by the Protocol, the collected tokens are destroyed in a heavy-duty shredder machine. The above procedures are regularly inspected by competent officers as well as by the Office of the Personal Data Protection Commissioner.

3. For the existing procedure (manual or ABC or both), please mention any **existing KPIs** to measure the **efficiency of the processes** and the **social acceptance of the Smart Border Control technologies**. If you have at your disposal the KPIs above grouped by demographics (age group, nationality, frequent traveler or not, relationship with technology...), please provide more information about them as well.

These various KPIs could include:

- **Time** (waiting time in queues, duration of border crossing during rush hour/on average/per season/overall vs individual processes, number of people treated per day...)
- **Usability of the system** (friendliness of Smart Border Control Technologies' user interface (biometrics devices, e-gates, kiosks...), ergonomics, passengers needing assistance...)
- **Accuracy** (Success/Failure rate, accuracy of biometrics...)
- **Robustness** (Downtime per month/year, Fallback options availability and interoperability...)
- **Security** (how do the systems address the following issues: fighting terrorism, illegal migration, reducing identity theft, overstayers...)

- **Privacy** (impact on Data Protection, privacy-by-design principles...)
- **Social implications** (impact on employment, percentage of society which is affected...)
- **Ethical implications** (cases of discrimination due to system failure to correctly identify individuals, impact on human rights, impact on equality – gender, social, racial...)
- **Flexibility** (possibility to adapt to different locations and border types...)
- **Quality of service - Satisfaction** (HappyOrNot's terminals, questionnaires...)

Make sure to include any historic data that could be used in these KPIs to assess the efficiency of the previous manual vs current processes.

In case these KPIs are not available as such, do/will we have access in order to collect the corresponding raw data? e.g. logs from BCP devices, software to measure queue size with a corresponding time thus average waiting time...

The contribution of the borderXpress kiosks in the execution of border checks has exceeded every expectation. In the first 12 months of operation, the kiosks processed more than five million passengers, contributing to the overall efficiency at border control areas and improving passenger queues. Positive results have also been tracked across several key customer satisfaction metrics. Also, both airports have significantly reduced passenger processing times, from between 50 to 80 seconds down to 15 to 30 seconds, essentially eliminating queues altogether.

In a report prepared by Xovis, the average exit immigration processing times at Larnaka Airport were assessed. For the week of July 1 to 7, 2019, the average wait time for passengers using a borderXpress kiosk was one minute. For those not using a borderXpress kiosk, the wait time increased to approximately five minutes—showcasing the considerable advantage this technology offers. More specifically, the below KPIs are measured in the context of passport control:

- Wait time for Third Country Nationals (no entry visa): 30-35 seconds per passenger
- Wait time for Third Country Nationals (entry visa): 1-1,5 minute per passenger
- Wait time for EU citizens (traditional checks): 15-20 seconds per passenger
- Wait time for EU citizens (borderXpress kiosks): 5 seconds per passenger
- Use of borderXpress kiosks at arrivals: 38%
- Use of borderXpress kiosks at departures: 43%

4. Please describe if there are **adaptations/new changes** to the current processes **foreseen** until the end of 2023.

If so, make sure to mention the changes foreseen (technologies, processes, use of biometrics) and how they might impact the METICOS pilot.

The competent authorities of the Republic of Cyprus are considering expanding the categories of persons who can use the borderXpress kiosks. Specifically, after the Brexit, and due to the fact that the majority of passengers who travel through the local Airports are citizens of the United Kingdom (U.K.), and depending on the Brexit agreement, it is being considered that specific kiosks could be used by some categories of low risk Third Country Nationals (TCNs), for whom a visa to cross the external border of EU is not required, such as citizens of the U.K., the U.S.A., Canada, Australia and New Zealand. However, in such a case, after the conclusion of the self-checks at the borderXpress kiosks, the border guard who collects the tokens will have to stamp the passengers' travel document. Furthermore, these passengers might be required to answer to some simple questions about their flight, return ticket, accommodation etc. in accordance with the entry requirements as defined by the SBC.

It is worth mentioning that the borderXpress kiosks are currently connected to the National Entry Exit System (EES). In case Cyprus joins Schengen and implements the European EES, the arrivals and departures of the above TCNs will be also registered to the European EES.

Additionally, it is being considered abolishing issuing tokens after the use of the borderXpress kiosks. In such a case, the implementation of a software to transfer the data in real time to the device of the border guard, will be needed. In this scenario, after the passengers conclude the self-check and while headed towards the border guard, will be split into two lanes, green and red, depending on the results of the check.

5. Please describe the categories of people that you envisage the METICOS project to measure their acceptance of the Smart Border technologies.

Some categories may include:

- *Travelers: passengers (Third Country Nationals, EU-citizens)*
- *Operational staff: border guards, customs, police authorities, immigration services...*
- *Other: civil society, data privacy experts, ethics and human rights experts...*

Police Boarder Control Officers and Immigration Officers working at the airports.

6. Please mention **other stakeholders**, apart from your authority/organization, which would need access to the social acceptance and impact that we will measure and are potential future users of the METICOS solution.

Some examples may include:

- *Operational: border guards, customs, police authorities, immigration services...*
- *Policy: EU Parliament, EC, EU Council, National policy makers...*
- *Technical: ABC systems and equipment manufacturers & responsible for maintenance of these systems...*

Police Boarder Control Officers, Immigration Officers working at the airports and Hermes Airports who is the operator of both local airports.

7. Do you have a **standalone Border Guard training center** (testing/non-operational setting or similar) that could be used in METICOS to deploy Smart Border Control technologies and evaluate their social acceptance in a structured and controlled manner? If not, is it foreseen to be deployed by 2023? (A similar setting was used in the PROTECT project; check [this link](#).)

No, Cyprus Police does not have an autonomous Border Guard training center that could be used in the METICOS program. It not expected to deploy such center soon.

8. Do you have a **standalone operational pilot setting** in the BCP where Smart Border Control technologies are deployed and could be used in METICOS to evaluate their social acceptance in a structured and controlled manner? If not, is it foreseen to be deployed by 2023? (A similar setting was used in the implementation of the ABC4EU project (check [this link](#)), where dedicated ABC gates were deployed, amongst other locations, in Madrid airport, apart from the standard existing processes used at the time.)

No, Cyprus Police does not have a standalone operational pilot setting at the border control checkpoints. If needed for the purpose of the project, a dedicated restricted area at the airport can be designated for executing any pilot testing.

9. Please specify for each BCP, which are the user groups will access the offered METICOS platform? Some groups may include: BCP staff, competent authorities etc.

Access to METICOS platform will be offered to the Immigration officers working for the Aliens and Immigration Unit- part of Cyprus Police who are competent to carry out border checks at Cyprus airports (Larnaca and Paphos airports).

10. Please specify for each user group who are the end-users?

Some end-users may include: managers, decision makers, practitioners etc.

- Immigration officers in Larnaca and Paphos airports who conduct immigration controls at Border Crossing Points (BCPs) throughout Cyprus, in accordance with EU and national law.
- The officer in charge of the BCP passport control who has the final decision-making power in respect of refusals of entry/exit to passengers arriving/departing to/from Cyprus airports.

11. Please specify for each end user a brief description of their activity and the procedures used in their activity?

Immigration officers:

Control of passengers is performed either manually by an Immigration Officer in a booth or by the use of an automated but supervised self-service processing solution depending on the citizenship of the passenger.

Non-EEA passengers:

All non-EEA passengers are subject to manual interactive examination by an Immigration Officer at a booth, to ensure that they comply with immigration rules and procedures.

Travellers present themselves and their travel documents for examination. The examination of passenger's travel documents is a central procedure of the immigration control process. Firstly, the Immigration Officer examines documents by eye, seeking to establish that the passenger is the rightful holder and not travelling on a passport belonging to another person. Immigration Officers also check documents to ensure that passengers have an appropriate visa, should this be required.

Travel documents are then inserted into a document reader device. The document reader captures and validates the Machine-Readable Zone details of the travel document and checks that the travel document is in possession of genuine features. Following that, it forwards the biographical information of the traveller to specific databases, national and international. This allows for real-time comparisons with traveller information and allows for the performance of checks to determine whether a passenger is using a passport previously reported as stolen or lost. (query INTERPOL's Stolen and Lost Travel Documents (SLTD) database) as well as the performance of checks on other national databases and border control records to determine eligibility of the passenger for border crossing. The Immigration Officer receives an alert when the passenger is perceived as a security threat or has any adverse immigration history (such as overstaying, working illegally, or being refused in the past).

The decision leave to enter for some cases is very straightforward; for instance, passengers will automatically be refused entry and held for further questioning if they present forged documents, or do not have a required visa. In other cases, the decision-making process is far more complex, and the Immigration Officer is required to assess the credibility of the passenger under control, based on the stated intentions and the individual circumstances of the passenger.

The majority of passengers are granted leave to enter after a brief interview at the control desk (e.g. about their personal circumstances and reasons for seeking entry to Cyprus); a few others are delayed for further questioning and then granted or refused leave to enter.

Factors which trigger further questioning for some passengers by the Immigration Officers are: the passengers' travel history, previous immigration law breaches or refusals of entry, the accuracy of the passenger stated purpose/intentions of his/her visit, the plausibility of a host/sponsor and the passengers' financial and other circumstances.

Chiefs of Immigration Officers have the final decision-making power in respect of refusals.

When the traveller completes entry/exit border clearance formalities, details of the arriving and departing flight are added, the data package is time stamped by the system to record the date of travel, and the travel record is added to the entry and exit database.

EEA passengers:

Self-service automated check is available only for the citizens enjoying the right of free movement in the European Union. A considerable number of interactive kiosks for a self-service automated check is also available for the citizens enjoying the right of free movement in the European Union. The use of the interactive kiosks is voluntary and the check performed verifies the identity of the traveller, the authenticity of his/her travel document and the absence or presence of alerts in national and international databases. Upon completion of the check, a token is issued to the passenger that must be presented to the Immigration officer who will allow entry or exit.

Officers in charge of the BCPs:

Provide line management, support and guidance for Immigration Officers in first-and second-line controls and have the final decision-making power in respect of refusals of entry/exit to passengers arriving/departing to/from Cyprus airports.

12. What data do end users need in their work?

For example, a user in the "BCP staff" user group who performs passport control needs the personal data of the person crossing the border. A user in the "Police- and Border Guard Board" user group needs certain data to evaluate the activity of the staff.

- The personal data of the person crossing the border
- National stop-list
- The INTERPOL SLTD database
- passenger's travel history to/from Cyprus - Entry and Departure Databases
- Database of residence permits issued by the State
- Civil registration, and national identity card and travel document issuance data
- Visa information data.

13. What are the currently used applications?

- BorderXpress Technology (the self-service check-in kiosks)
- Document readers
- National Entry and Departure System (custom made application).

14. In order to meet the objectives of the project, please specify the end-user requirements to be met by METICOS platform?

Please answer this question with a "story" on the day-to-day work and how the METICOS platform can help you. For example, for a user in the user group "BCP staff" who performs passport control which are the activities performed. This description is needed to identify the needs that the METICOS platform needs to cover. These activity descriptions are required for each user in the user group.

- Only necessary and relevant information should be kept on the platform according to the national data protection and privacy legislation
- The platform should be integrated with national and international databases
- 24/7/365 operational support
- Appropriate business continuity and disaster recovery arrangements required
- Travellers should not be able to view equipment or the screens displayed to Immigration officers
- Access to the platform should be controlled
- The use of and access to the platform should be audited and transactions logged, so that any misuse can be clearly identified

- Traveller processing time-The transaction time should meet the international standards for the clearance of people entering or departing Cyprus by air
- Proper training of the Immigration Officers for the use of the platform.

Hellenic Police

1. Please specify the Border Control Point(s) (BCP) that the pilot will take place.

For each BCP, we would like to know:

- *the exact location*
- *the type of border (air, land, sea...)*
- *traffic mix (for instance for land borders, people crossing border on foot, personal vehicles, public transport, cargo vehicles...)*
- *traffic (how many crossings per day)*
- *any relevant information regarding the pilot location (challenges the border guards and authorities have to face...)*

The BCP that the pilot will take place is Athens International Airport, which is an air BCP.

Regarding the traffic mix that the border guards have to handle, it consists of airplane passengers, airplane pilots and staff, staff working on cargo airplanes, passengers on private flights.

The traffic is approximately 30K per day (entry: 10K EU, 5K TCN, EXIT 10K EU, 5K TCN). The main challenges the airport authorities and the border guards have to face are to secure that the persons moving into the airport cannot pose a threat to its security and to manage the traffic in an efficient and effective manner, in order to avoid delays during the procedures (e.g. security checks, border checks) which take place.

2. Please describe the **process(es)** that are being used at the Border Control Point. Please include no-gate control technologies and manual operations (if they are still being used), for which you want to measure the social acceptance.

BCP staff carries out checks against the relevant data bases (international, EU and national) on a daily and systematic basis for the detection of possible illegal crossings during the entry and exit of the travellers, both EU citizens and third country nationals (TCNs), at the external borders of the EU. The BCP staff is responsible for deciding whether a person fulfils the preconditions of article 6 of the SBC, in order to allow for his / her entry. For TCNs, thorough checks are being performed as well, which consist of systematic checks and interviewing.

Make sure to include:

- *what **technologies** are being used. For instance, if an Automated Border Control (ABC) gate is in use, specify if it is integrated with the processes or standalone, if there are one or two steps in the process of the border control passage etc. Please make sure to include if a pre-border check is currently operational (use of kiosks)*
Passport readers, fingerprints, scanners, portable and non-portable UV counterfeit document detectors and magnifiers. In Athens International Airport e-gates are deployed and they are used only by EU citizens.
- *what **raw data** are being gathered to measure the performance of the process.*

- *availability of the above **data grouped** by demographics (age group, nationality, level of education...)*
Nationality (EU, TCNs)

- *the type of biometrics being used (Facial Image (FI), FingerPrints (FP) & how many, Iris) and at which process(es)/stage(s) of the process each (pre-enrolment, authentication and verification, border passage entry/exit ...)*
Facial Image and Fingerprints are used by BCP Staff at all control levels.

3. For the existing procedure (manual or ABC or both), please mention any **existing KPIs** to measure the **efficiency of the processes** and the **social acceptance of the Smart Border Control technologies**. If you have at your disposal the KPIs above grouped by demographics (age group, nationality, frequent traveler or not, relationship with technology...), please provide more information about them as well.

These various KPIs could include:

- **Time** (waiting time in queues, duration of border crossing during rush hour/on average/per season/overall vs individual processes, number of people treated per day...)
- **Usability of the system** (friendliness of Smart Border Control Technologies' user interface (biometrics devices, e-gates, kiosks...), ergonomics, passengers needing assistance...)
- **Accuracy** (Success/Failure rate, accuracy of biometrics...)
- **Robustness** (Downtime per month/year, Fallback options availability and interoperability...)
- **Security** (how do the systems address the following issues: fighting terrorism, illegal migration, reducing identity theft, overstayers...)
- **Privacy** (impact on Data Protection, privacy-by-design principles...)
- **Social implications** (impact on employment, percentage of society which is affected...)
- **Ethical implications** (cases of discrimination due to system failure to correctly identify individuals, impact on human rights, impact on equality – gender, social, racial...)
- **Flexibility** (possibility to adapt to different locations and border types...)
- **Quality of service - Satisfaction** (HappyOrNot's terminals, questionnaires...)

Make sure to include any historic data that could be used in these KPIs to assess the efficiency of the previous manual vs current processes.

In case these KPIs are not available as such, do/will we have access in order to collect the corresponding raw data? e.g. logs from BCP devices, software to measure queue size with a corresponding time thus average waiting time...

No KPIs currently in use.

4. Please describe if there are **adaptations/new changes** to the current processes **foreseen** until the end of 2023.

If so, make sure to mention the changes foreseen (technologies, processes, use of biometrics) and how they might impact the METICOS pilot.

Until the end of 2023, Hellenic Police will implement APIS directive, ETIAS regulation and EES regulation.

The implementation of the above mentioned directive and regulations will change the passport-control procedures, smart border methods will be applied.

5. Please describe the categories of people that you envisage the METICOS project to measure their acceptance of the Smart Border technologies.

Some categories may include:

- *Travelers: passengers (Third Country Nationals, EU-citizens)*
- *Operational staff: border guards, customs, police authorities, immigration services...*
- *Other: civil society, data privacy experts, ethics and human rights experts...*

BCP staff, EU and third country nationals (TCNs), Law enforcement authorities, passenger carriers.
All of the above in each type of BCP (Air, Sea, Land).

6. Please mention **other stakeholders**, apart from your authority/organization, which would need access to the social acceptance and impact that we will measure and are potential future users of the METICOS solution.

Some examples may include:

- *Operational: border guards, customs, police authorities, immigration services...*
- *Policy: EU Parliament, EC, EU Council, National policy makers...*
- *Technical: ABC systems and equipment manufacturers & responsible for maintenance of these systems...*

7. Do you have a **standalone Border Guard training center** (testing/non-operational setting or similar) that could be used in METICOS to deploy Smart Border Control technologies and evaluate their social acceptance in a structured and controlled manner? If not, is it foreseen to be deployed by 2023? (A similar setting was used in the PROTECT project; check [this link](#).)

8. Do you have a **standalone operational pilot setting** in the BCP where Smart Border Control technologies are deployed and could be used in METICOS to evaluate their social acceptance in a structured and controlled manner? If not, is it foreseen to be deployed by 2023? (A similar setting was used in the implementation of the ABC4EU project (check [this link](#)), where dedicated ABC gates were deployed, amongst other locations, in Madrid airport, apart from the standard existing processes used at the time.)

E-gates are deployed in Athens International Airport and we think that METICOS could be used to evaluate its acceptance in a structured and controlled manner.

9. Please specify for each BCP, which are the user groups will access the offered METICOS platform? Some groups may include: BCP staff, competent authorities etc.

*BCP staff, EU and third country nationals (TCNs), Law enforcement authorities.
All of the above in each type of BCP (Air, Sea, Land).*

10. Please specify for each user group who are the end-users?

Some end-users may include: managers, decision makers, practitioners etc.

- BCP Staff: Border Guard Authorities, Facility Security Staff (Airport/Port), Customs Authorities

- Law enforcement authorities: Police Staff (Airports, Land Borders), Coast Guard (Ports).

11. Please specify for each end user a brief description of their activity and the procedures used in their activity?

BCP staff carries out checks against the relevant data bases (international, EU and national) on a daily and systematic basis for the detection of possible illegal crossings during the entry and exit of the travellers, both EU citizens and third country nationals (TCNs), at the external borders of the EU. The BCP staff is responsible for deciding whether a person fulfils the preconditions of article 6 of the SBC, in order to allow for his / her entry. For TCNs, thorough checks are being performed as well, which consist of systematic checks and interviewing.

12. What data do end users need in their work?

For example, a user in the “BCP staff” user group who performs passport control needs the personal data of the person crossing the border. A user in the "Police- and Border Guard Board" user group needs certain data to evaluate the activity of the staff.

[BCP staff user group who performs passport control needs the personal data of the person crossing the border.](#)

13. What are the currently used applications?

14. In order to meet the objectives of the project, please specify the end-user requirements to be met by METICOS platform?

Please answer this question with a "story" on the day-to-day work and how the METICOS platform can help you. For example, for a user in the user group "BCP staff" who performs passport control which are the activities performed. This description is needed to identify the needs that the METICOS platform needs to cover. These activity descriptions are required for each user in the user group.

[The implementation of METICOS platform will offer a more modern and efficient Smart Border, offering a very useful tool at end users.](#)

[The platform METICOS should:](#)

- [ensure the interoperability of all the relevant data bases used by the end-users at the borders and an automated use of the data,](#)
- [be user-friendly for all the user groups](#)
- [be fast, efficient and secure for the personal data of the travellers](#)
- [ensure social acceptance through an information campaign](#)
- [ensure an easy and fast Big Data processing and analysis](#)

Politsei- ja Piirivalveamet

1. Please specify the **Border Control Point(s) (BCP)** that the pilot will take place.

For each BCP, we would like to know:

- *the exact location*
[Tallinn-11 BCP \(Old City Harbour\)](#)
- *the type of border (air, land, sea...)*
[Sea border](#)
- *traffic mix (for instance for land borders, people crossing border on foot, personal vehicles, public transport, cargo vehicles...)*
[People crossing on foot and by car, also cargo vehicles](#)
- *traffic (how many crossings per day)*
[In 2019: Once a week enters and exits regular ferry Princess Anastasia from Russia and usually there are 1500 passengers on it.](#)
- *any relevant information regarding the pilot location (challenges the border guards and authorities have to face...)*
[We have to inform about the pilot Tallinn port authorities.](#)

2. Please describe the **process(es)** that are being used at the Border Control Point. Please include no-gate control technologies and manual operations (if they are still being used), for which you want to measure the social acceptance.

Make sure to include:

- *what **technologies** are being used. For instance, if an Automated Border Control (ABC) gate is in use, specify if it is integrated with the processes or standalone, if there are one or two steps in the process of the border control passage etc. Please make sure to include if a pre-border check is currently operational (use of kiosks)*
Border checks on persons are carried out accordingly to SPE. On entry and exit, third-country nationals are being subject to thorough checks. All persons crossing the external border are controlled and registered in Border Control Information System (PIKO).
- *what **raw data** are being gathered to measure the performance of the process*
Data that is being gathered: first name, last name, birth date, gender, document number, document issuing country, type of document (passport, ID-card, etc.), visa or residence permit data (number, type, validation).
- *availability of the above **data grouped** by demographics (age group, nationality, level of education...)*
Age group, gender, nationality
- *the type of biometrics being used (Facial Image (FI), FingerPrints (FP) & how many, Iris) and at which process(es)/stage(s) of the process each (pre-enrolment, authentication and verification, border passage entry/exit ...)*
Today we take one FP from a person, who is crossing the border with Schengen visa and make with that FP a request to CS-VIS. From CS-VIS we also get FI.

3. For the existing procedure (manual or ABC or both), please mention any **existing KPIs** (Key Performance Indicators) to measure the **efficiency of the processes** and the **social acceptance of the Smart Border Control technologies**. If you have at your disposal the KPIs above grouped by demographics (age group, nationality, frequent traveler or not, relationship with technology...), please provide more information about them as well.

These various KPIs could include:

- ***Time** (waiting time in queues, duration of border crossing during rush hour/on average/per season/overall vs individual processes, number of people treated per day...)*
We measure the border control duration by person (TCN and EU).
- ***Usability of the system** (friendliness of Smart Border Control Technologies' user interface (biometrics devices, e-gates, kiosks...), ergonomics, passengers needing assistance...)*
Today we don't measure it
- ***Accuracy** (Success/Failure rate, accuracy of biometrics...)*
Today we don't measure it
- ***Robustness** (Downtime per month/year, Fallback options availability and interoperability...)*
PIKO is allowed by its regulations to have 10 min per week downtime.
- ***Security** (how do the systems address the following issues: fighting terrorism, illegal migration, reducing identity theft, overstayers...)*
PIKO makes requests to internal and external information systems, e.g PIKO profiles, misdemeanour information system, SIS, Interpol, CS-VIS.
- ***Privacy** (impact on Data Protection, privacy-by-design principles...)*
Privacy and Data protection is described in PIKO regulation (official name in Estonian "Piirikontrolli andmekogu põhimäärus". The legal background in Data Protection to PIKO regulation comes mainly from Public Information Act and other acts, which are legally binding to the matter (such as Personal Data Protection Act and GDPR). Access to PIKO is granted only to the officers whose everyday working tasks require the access; usage of PIKO is logged and monitored. Cases of misuse and data breach are reported to The Data Protection Inspectorate (if needed).
- ***Social implications** (impact on employment, percentage of society which is affected...)*

Today we don't measure it

- **Ethical implications** (cases of discrimination due to system failure to correctly identify individuals, impact on human rights, impact on equality – gender, social, racial...)

Today we don't measure it

- **Flexibility** (possibility to adapt to different locations and border types...)

PIKO software is in mobile devices, which can be carried around.

Also, there is developed a mobile border control booth, which is located in Tallinn-11 BCP D-terminal and can be moved around from one location to another.

- **Quality of service - Satisfaction** (HappyOrNot's terminals, questionnaires...)

Today we don't measure it

Make sure to include any historic data that could be used in these KPIs to assess the efficiency of the previous manual vs current processes.

In case these KPIs are not available as such, do/will we have access in order to collect the corresponding raw data? e.g. logs from BCP devices, software to measure queue size with a corresponding time thus average waiting time...

4. Please describe if there are **adaptations/new changes** to the current processes **foreseen** until the end of 2023.

If so, make sure to mention the changes foreseen (technologies, processes, use of biometrics) and how they might impact the METICOS pilot.

By the end of 2023 PIKO will be already integrated with Entry-Exit System and ETIAS.

5. Please describe the categories of people that you envisage the METICOS project to measure their acceptance of the Smart Border technologies.

Some categories may include:

- *Travelers: passengers (Third Country Nationals, EU-citizens)*
- *Operational staff: border guards, customs, police authorities, immigration services...*
- *Other: civil society, data privacy experts, ethics and human rights experts...*

In the pilot we only use cadets from Estonian Academy of Security Sciences

6. Please mention **other stakeholders**, apart from your authority/organization, which would need access to the social acceptance and impact that we will measure and are potential future users of the METICOS solution.

Some examples may include:

- *Operational: border guards, customs, police authorities, immigration services...*
- *Policy: EU Parliament, EC, EU Council, National policy makers...*
- *Technical: ABC systems and equipment manufacturers & responsible for maintenance of these systems...*

No additional stakeholders are used, except Estonian Academy of Security Sciences, because the test objects to cross the borders will be cadets.

7. Do you have a **standalone Border Guard training center** (testing/non-operational setting or similar) that could be used in METICOS to deploy Smart Border Control technologies and evaluate their social acceptance in a structured and controlled manner? If not, is it foreseen to be deployed by 2023? (A similar setting was used in the PROTECT project; check [this link](#).)

Yes, in Estonia we have Estonian Academy of Security Sciences
<https://www.sisekaitse.ee/en/estonian-academy-security-sciences>

8. Do you have a **standalone operational pilot setting** in the BCP where Smart Border Control technologies are deployed and could be used in METICOS to evaluate their social acceptance in a structured and controlled manner? If not, is it foreseen to be deployed by 2023? (A similar setting was used in the implementation of the *ABC4EU* project (check [this link](#)), where dedicated ABC gates were deployed, amongst other locations, in Madrid airport, apart from the standard existing processes used at the time.)
Tallinn-11 BCP (Old City Harbour) A and B terminal
9. Please specify for each BCP, which are the user groups will access the offered METICOS platform? Some groups may include: BCP staff, competent authorities etc.
METICOS platform will be accessed by Police- and Border Guard Board and BCP staff.
10. Please specify for each user group who are the end-users? Some end-users may include: managers, decision makers, practitioners etc.
The specified user group will be Police-and Border Guard Boards decision makers and practitoners.
11. Please specify for each end user a brief description of their activity and the procedures used in their activity?
Police- and Border Guard Board will evaluate the activity, usability and procedures of the METICOS platform.
BCP staff will be doing the border control procedures.
Cadets from Estonian Academy of Security Sciences will play the border crossers.
12. What data do end users need in their work?
Currently we use data related to personal data (name, birthdate, etc.) and document data, some cases biometric data (FP – TCN Schengen visa users).
Types of data being managed: first name, last name, birth date, gender, document number, document issuing country, type of document (passport, ID-card, etc.), visa or residence permit data (number, type, validation).
13. What are the currently used applications?
Currently we use National Border Guard Information System (PIKO), also REGULA scanner (which is interpreted with document control software) to scan document data into PIKO.
PIKO makes requests to national databases (National Visa Register, Police database, Identity documents database, etc.) and external databases (SIS, Interpol, CS-VIS).
14. In order to meet the objectives of the project, please specify the end-user requirements to be met by METICOS platform? (just a brief overview that should be discuss in the future meetings).
The end-user has to be trained to be able to use the METICOS platform.
METICOS platform has to be easy to use, user friendly and avoided must be unnecessary clicks.

ITPF TIMISOARA

1. Please specify the **Border Control Point(s) (BCP)** that the pilot will take place.

BCP Stamora – Moravița and BCP Jimbolia

For each BCP, we would like to know:

- *the exact location*

BCP Stamora – Moravița (Moravița village);

BCP Jimbolia – about 4 km from Jimbolia village;

- *the type of border (air, land, sea...)*

Land for both BCP's

- *traffic mix (for instance for land borders, people crossing border on foot, personal vehicles, public transport, cargo vehicles...)*

People crossing border on foot, personal vehicles, cargo vehicles, international passenger transport;

- *traffic (how many crossings per day)*

Between 300 – 700 persons per day, depending on each period of year / day (e.g. summer time, different events in Serbia);

- *any relevant information regarding the pilot location (challenges the border guards and authorities have to face...)*

At present, the border crossing points in question (Moravița and Jimbolia) have a complex operational situation, facing various facts that may constitute crimes or misdemeanors. Thus, at the level of the two border crossing points, false or falsified travel documents were discovered, documents attesting the false or falsified quality of the driver, persons hidden in the means of transportation in order to enter Romania illegally, smuggling cigarettes and alcohol, etc ...)

2. Please describe the **process(es)** that are being used at the Border Control Point. Please include no-gate control technologies and manual operations (if they are still being used), for which you want to measure the social acceptance.

Make sure to include:

- *what **technologies** are being used. For instance, if an Automated Border Control (ABC) gate is in use, specify if it is integrated with the processes or standalone, if there are one or two steps in the process of the border control passage etc. Please make sure to include if a pre-border check is currently operational (use of kiosks)*

In Moravița and Jimbolia border crossing points, there is no automatic system for verifying the identity of persons. The check is carried out by the border policeman, based on the travel documents presented by the persons at the border control, following the interrogation of the national and international databases and the verification of the security elements of the travel documents.

- *what **rawdata** are being gathered to measure the performance of the process*

Personal identification data of passengers

- *availability of the above **data grouped** by demographics (age group, nationality, level of education...)*

At present, we have just data referring to passenger nationality – Third Country citizens and EU citizens).

- *the type of biometrics being used (Facial Image (FI), FingerPrints (FP) & how many, Iris) and at which process(es)/stage(s) of the process each (pre-enrolment, authentication and verification, border passage entry/exit ...)*

At the moment, the border guards use the biometric data entered in the CIP of the travel documents (facial image - Facial Image and digital impression - FingerPrints), but there is no technology to verify this biometric data

3. For the existing procedure (manual or ABC or both), please mention any **existing KPIs** to measure the **efficiency of the processes** and the **social acceptance of the Smart Border Control technologies**. If you have at your disposal the KPIs above grouped by demographics (age group, nationality, frequent traveler or not, relationship with technology...), please provide more information about them as well.

These various KPIs could include:

- **Time** (waiting time in queues, duration of border crossing during rush hour/on average/per season/overall vs individual processes, number of people treated per day...)
- **Usability of the system** (friendliness of Smart Border Control Technologies' user interface (biometrics devices, e-gates, kiosks...), ergonomics, passengers needing assistance...)
- **Accuracy** (Success/Failure rate, accuracy of biometrics...)
- **Robustness** (Downtime per month/year, Fallback options availability and interoperability...)
- **Security** (how do the systems address the following issues: fighting terrorism, illegal migration, reducing identity theft, overstayers...)
- **Privacy** (impact on Data Protection, privacy-by-design principles...)
- **Social implications** (impact on employment, percentage of society which is affected...)
- **Ethical implications** (cases of discrimination due to system failure to correctly identify individuals, impact on human rights, impact on equality – gender, social, racial...)
- **Flexibility** (possibility to adapt to different locations and border types...)
- **Quality of service - Satisfaction** (HappyOrNot's terminals, questionnaires...)

Make sure to include any historic data that could be used in these KPIs to assess the efficiency of the previous manual vs current processes.

In case these KPIs are not available as such, do/will we have access in order to collect the corresponding raw data? e.g. logs from BCP devices, software to measure queue size with a corresponding time thus average waiting time...

NO existing KPIs to measure the efficiency of the processes and the social acceptance of the Smart Border Control technologies.

4. Please describe if there are **adaptations/new changes** to the current processes **foreseen** until the end of 2023.

If so, make sure to mention the changes foreseen (technologies, processes, use of biometrics) and how they might impact the METICOS pilot.

NO adaptations/new changes to the current processes foreseen until the end of 2023.

5. Please describe the categories of people that you envisage the METICOS project to measure their acceptance of the Smart Border technologies.

Some categories may include:

- **Travelers: passengers (Third Country Nationals, EU-citizens)**
- **Operational staff: border guards, customs, police authorities, immigration services...**

Travelers: passengers from Third Countries, EU-citizens, stateless persons;
Operational staff: border guards and customs officers;

- **Other: civil society, data privacy experts, ethics and human rights experts.**

Other – No;

6. Please mention **other stakeholders**, apart from your authority/organization, which would need access to the social acceptance and impact that we will measure and are potential future users of the METICOS solution.

Some examples may include:

- *Operational: border guards, customs, police authorities, immigration services...*

Operational: border guards, customs officers, police authorities, immigration service;

- *Policy: EU Parliament, EC, EU Council, National policy makers...*

Policy: National Policy Makers;

- *Technical: ABC systems and equipment manufacturers & responsible for maintenance of these systems...*

Technical: ABC systems and equipment manufacturers and responsible for maintenance of these systems;

7. Do you have a **standalone Border Guard training center** (testing/non-operational setting or similar) that could be used in METICOS to deploy Smart Border Control technologies and evaluate their social acceptance in a structured and controlled manner? If not, is it foreseen to be deployed by 2023?(A similar setting was used in the PROTECT project; check [this link](#).)

The Headquarter of Timisoara Territorial Inspectorate of Border Police);

8. Do you have a **standalone operational pilot setting** in the BCP where Smart Border Control technologies are deployed and could be used in METICOS to evaluate their social acceptance in a structured and controlled manner? If not, is it foreseen to be deployed by 2023? (A similar setting was used in the implementation of the ABC4EU project (check [this link](#)), where dedicated ABC gates were deployed, amongst other locations, in Madrid airport, apart from the standard existing processes used at the time.)

There is NO standalone operational pilot setting in the BCP where Smart Border Control technologies are deployed.

9. Please specify for each BCP, which are the user groups will access the offered METICOS platform?

Some groups may include: BCP staff, competent authorities etc.

Headquarter staff, B.P.U. staff and B.C.P. staff

10. Please specify for each user group who are the end-users?

Some end-users may include: managers, decision makers, practitioners etc.

Headquarter staff – the end users are represented by the chief of Timisoara Territorial Inspectorate of Border Police and the deputy chief of Timisoara Territorial Inspectorate of Border Police)

B.P.U. staff – the end users are represented by the chief of the Border Police Unit, the deputy of the Border Police Unit, as well as the officers from the Surveillance and Border Control Compartments and Prevention and Combat of Illegal Migration and Cross-border Crime Compartments.

B.C.P. staff – the end users are represented by the chief of the Border Crossing Point, First line officers, Second Line Officers and Group Coordinators.

11. Please specify for each end user a brief description of their activity and the procedures used in their activity?

Headquarter

The Chief of Timisoara Territorial Inspectorate of Border Police orders measures which have to be followed by all the subordinated structures;

The deputy chief of Timisoara Territorial Inspectorate of Border Police orders measures which have to be followed by all the subordinated structures, especially by the operational structures.

Border Police Unit

The chief of the Border Police Unit takes measures in order to implement all the orders of the Chief of Timisoara Territorial Inspectorate of Border Police, organizes and coordinates all the activities of the BPU. The deputy chief of the Border Police Unit, coordinates the operative officers and takes measures to implement the orders of the chief of the Border Police Unit.

The Officers from the Surveillance and Border Control Compartments – follow to implement the orders of deputy chief and the chief of border police unit, elaborate points of view regarding the improvement of the activities which take place in the border crossing point, realize training activities with the border guards who work in the border crossing points, etc.

The Officers from Prevention and Combat of Illegal Migration and Cross-border Crime Compartments – their main activity is to carry out all the procedural acts regarding criminal investigation. It is the department specialized in preventing and combating illegal migration.

Border Crossing Point

The chief of the Border Crossing Point – organizes all the activities within the Border Crossing Point and follows that all measures ordered by the chief of BPU are respected by the border guards.

The Group coordinators (one per each working shift) – follow that all measures given by the chief border crossing point are respected, follow that police officers from first line respect the legislation, as well as all the procedures relevant in their activity. They always keep in touch with the chief of the BCP and report him all the measures taken on their shift.

The first line officers – verify the identity and the nationality of the persons that cross the BCP, as well as the authenticity and validity of the travel document. They also verify the means of transport and the objects that are transported inside in order to make sure that they are not likely to jeopardise the public order, internal security, public health or international relations of any of the Member States. They also query the data bases regarding the alerts on persons and, when necessary, the objects included in the SIS and other relevant Union databases.

The Second line officers – carry out additional checks on the persons sent in the second line, by the border guard from the first line, by querying the databases and establishing the legal status of the persons, means of transport and objects.

12. What data do end users need in their work?

For example, a user in the “BCP staff” user group who performs passport control needs the personal data of the person crossing the border. A user in the “Police- and Border Guard Board” user group needs certain data to evaluate the activity of the staff.

The chief of Timisoara Territorial Inspectorate of Border Police – all data provided by the BPU;

The deputy Chief of Timisoara Territorial Inspectorate of Border Police – all data provided by the BPU;

The chief of the Border Police Unit– all data provided by the BCP;

The deputy chief of the Border Police Unit– all data provided by the BCP;

The officers from the Surveillance and Border Control Compartments – all data regarding passenger nationality, the number of the persons who cross the border, etc.

The officers from Prevention and Combat of Illegal Migration and Cross-border Crime Compartments – all data regarding the illegal migration, smuggling, terrorism, etc.

The first line officers – biometric data, identification data provided by the travel documents, license plates, vehicle insurances and other documents which allow the persons to cross the border.

The second line officers – the same data like the first line officers, other documents which are necessary to establish the legal status of persons, in order to allow or forbid them to cross the border

13. What are the currently used applications?

At this moment, the Border Police use the internal and external applications in order to establish the legal status of persons who cross the border.

14. In order to meet the objectives of the project, please specify the end-user requirements to be met by METICOS platform?

Please answer this question with a "story" on the day-to-day work and how the METICOS platform can help you. For example, for a user in the user group "BCP staff" who performs passport control which are the activities performed. This description is needed to identify the needs that the METICOS platform needs to cover. These activity descriptions are required for each user in the user group.

The first line officers carry out border checks in order to identify all data provided by the travel documents, license plates, vehicle insurances and other documents which a person needs in order to cross the border. In order to verify all data, the police officers query all national databases, and, when needed, they also query the international databases.

APPENDIX II: Technologies and capabilities template

General Introduction and Instructions

Objective:	The objective of this Template/Questionnaire is to provide high and medium level descriptions of Technologies (and their capabilities) available on the METICOS Project. This information will be used to inform the user requirements, system specifications, use cases and architectural design of the METICOS Platform.
Technology types included	By technologies in this template we mean any technology (made available by METICOS Technology Provider Partners) including IT (software or hardware) components/modules and equipment (e.g Sensors).
Structure of Template	This template contains two tables (on the next two sheets). The first gives a high level description of Technologies/Components in METICOS, the later describes functionalities of the Technology (existing or proposed to be developed within this Project)
Final remarks	All partners are invited to fill in this template once per each technology they make available (e.g. if you have/are responsible for 3 technologies/components fill in the template once for each, in total 3 times).
	Detailed instructions for filling in each field can be seen by clicking on that field (provided you have a recent version of Excel).
	For any questions regarding this template please contact Andrei.Ogrezeanu@Siveco.ro and Radu.Gaza@Siveco.ro

Technology Description

	Please read the Instructions Sheet prior to filling in this Table!
Responsible Partner Abbreviated Name (per DOA)	Abbreviated name of partner in charge of developing, or implementing the technology within METICOS. Use the abbreviations in the Project Description of Action.
Technology/Component Name within METICOS	Technology or Component Name within the METICOS Project

Technology/Component Other Internal Name	Indicate if the technology has a name outside the METICOS project (e.g. the technology may have been developed in a different Project with a different name)
Corresponding Task in METICOS	If already clear to you from DoA in which task this technology/component will be developed/integrated please mention its number (e.g. 6.2). If not, answer "Not known"
Is the technology developed/owned by Responsible Partner or third party?	Indicate whether the technology is owned/developed by your organization or it is developed by a third party or is open source, etc.. Please mention who is the third party if this is the case.
Current Technology Readiness Level (TRL)	
Planned Technology Readiness (TRL) by the end of METICOS	
Technology/Component History	Please mention when technology was developed to reach the current TRL level. Was it developed under another project? Was the project financed internally or externally (e.g. by EC).
Technology/Component in the Present: Description	Give a summary overview of what the technology does (NOW) in terms of actions that can be accomplished with it. Please make the text understandable for someone outside your organization who is not necessarily specialized in the technology/component.
Technology/Component at the End of Project: Description	Give a summary overview of what the technology will do AT THE END OF PROJECT. Please make the text understandable for someone outside your organization who is not necessarily specialized in the technology/component.
Technology at the End Of Project: Benefits	Indicate the benefits (goals that can be achieved) for the technology users
Data Input Requirements	Indicate in this field the following: what data this component needs (variables needed); where from (from other components, from outside sources, are you generating the data?)
Expected Data Output	Indicate what is the data output the component produces (in terms of main variables produced). Also based on your current understanding, is your data output an input for other components? Which ones?
Hardware/Networking (Low Level) Interfaces	Describe hardware/networking interfaces e.g.: - Wi-Fi, Ethernet, VPN, xG, etc. - Hardware interfaces plug-in types (Power Supply and Communications)
Software Interfaces (protocols, file types, standards)	Describe software interfaces (protocols, file types, standards, e.g. API, REST, RPC, Web Services, etc.).
Other Information, Observations, etc.	

Capabilities

Technology/Component:		Responsible Partner:			
Capability/Functionality Title	Description	User roles	Current Maturity/Readiness (TRL)	Proposed Priority Level	Interface (service, methods, data structures)
Title of the capability/functionality. Suggested length 1-5 words. Title should include a verb that describes the action performed by functionality. Example answers: "Display Intervention Vehicles on a Map"; "Search content by keywords", etc.	Describe what that capability/functionality does. Make sure it is something understandable by someone outside your team working on that component.	Without having yet a standardized list of user roles, list from your point of view who (user roles, organizational positions at end users) who would likely use this capability/functionality			Provide a detailed description of services, methods (method signature including parameters, name and type) and data structures.

Other instructions: Please list both back end and front end capabilities related to your component. Please add descriptions of user facing capabilities/functionalities. Even if technically these will be in the GUI (and it remains to be seen based on Architecture, whether the GUI will be at component level or a common GUI for the entire METICOS System), it is up to you to define what the user facing capabilities related to your component will be. What kind of reports will be served to users based on this tool? What are the main elements, data, etc. present in those reports?

Only if your component is aimed only at serving other components then it does not have user facing capabilities/functionalities.